

Master's Thesis

International University of Applied Sciences

Master of Science, Data Management

**Performance Analysis and Comparison of Quantized Language Models
on Resource Constraints - The Case of Supply Chain Risk Data.**

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II Abstract

This thesis investigates the performance analysis and comparison of quantized language models (LLMs) in resource-constrained environments, focusing on supply chain risk data. As large language models expand rapidly, there is a pressing need for compact AI solutions compatible with low-memory footprints and reduced power consumption, particularly in resource-limited settings. This research targets the unique challenges of these environments, specifically hardware limitations. Developers aim to create lightweight AI models that maintain acceptable accuracy levels while minimizing size, execution speeds, and energy demands.

The research investigates the potential of WasmEdge as a promising solution for executing light-weight language models on WebAssembly modules beyond browser environments, unlocking the potential of LLMs in resource-constrained settings.

In conclusion, this research proposes a novel technique for deploying quantized lightweight LLMs for inference generation on resource-constrained environments using Supply Chain Risk Management data. The study reveals a strong correlation between inference quality, inference duration, and performance metrics within these models. Notably, shorter inference times and better performance efficiency do not always equate to best inference quality. It provides valuable insights that contribute to the development of efficient and accessible AI models. The findings push advancements in AI-assisted supply chain risk management applications and beyond.

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VI Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DL	Deep Learning
FC	Feedforward Connections
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GTX	GigaTexel Shader eXtreme (a line of graphics cards by Nvidia)
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
LLMs	Language Learning Models
LLaMA_CPP	Large Language Model with Attention Mechanism implemented in C++
MOE	Mixture of Experts
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OS	Operating System
PTQ	Post-Training Quantization
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface for Unix.
QAT	Quantization-aware Training
RAM	Random Access Memory
SCRM	Supply Chain Risk Management
SMoE	Sparse Mixtures of Experts
SRAM	Static Random Access Memory
SSD	Solid State Drive
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VRAM	Virtual-Random Access Memory
WASM	WebAssembly (Low-level bytecode format that runs in web browsers)

1 Introduction

Language models (LLMs) are emerging as pivotal tools in supply chain management, facilitating advanced data analysis and decision-making processes. However, research in this space in relation to Big Data, AI and supply chain appears quite dispersed, as noted by Zamani et al. (2022)

Prior to this new development, supply chain management had been achieved, first with traditional means, and later with proprietary software applications that are able to track, record and monitor supply chain pipelines. Some notable ones include E2open, SAP SCM, Logility, Perfect Commerce, and Oracle SCM, which are leading supply chain management software solutions offering comprehensive features to streamline operations and enhance efficiency. (Relia Software, 2020) E2open focuses on responsive and demand-driven supply chains, offering integrated modules for monitoring, analytics, planning, and collaboration. SAP SCM leverages advanced technologies like AI and IoT for full visibility and real-time decision-making across the supply chain. Oracle SCM provides end-to-end visibility and streamlined processes, empowering businesses to innovate and optimize operations from product development to order fulfilment. These solutions cater to diverse business needs, helping organizations stay competitive in dynamic market environments.

While supply chain management has historically relied on traditional methods and proprietary software applications, the emergence of artificial intelligence and machine learning is gradually bringing about a paradigm shift. Artificial Intelligence is gradually being adopted in tools for analyzing supply chain management. (Relia Software, 2020)

Despite this developments, the research, development and adoption of Language models (LLMs) in the realm of supply chain management is quite slow. As this adoption increases, small organisations working on supply chain management might have to deploy such technologies with its associated computational demands, which many will not be ready for. The deployment of LLMs in such enterprises constrained by limited resources will pose distinct challenges, especially in the context of small businesses where computational capabilities may be restricted. This study seeks to explore the performance dynamics of various quantized LLMs operating within such constraints, with a dedicated emphasis on their application in analyzing supply chain risks for small enterprises.

The significance of LLMs underscores the critical need to assess their efficacy in resource-constrained settings, where the stakes for performance optimization are particularly high. By scrutinizing the performance of quantized LLMs in small business environments, this research seeks to address a pertinent gap in the existing literature and provide actionable insights for practitioners. The main goal is to shed more light on the nuanced relationship between quantization, model parameters, resource utilization and deployment platforms, thereby informing strategic decisions regarding LLM implementation in real-world scenarios.

This study is motivated by the importance of connecting the latest advances in LLM technology with real-world supply chain management demands, particularly for small businesses that typically run on strict budgets and have limited resources. Our objective is to explore the benefits of using carefully adapted LLMs based on specific needs and restrictions of small businesses. We seek to reveal the advantages of using quantized LLMs in reducing supply chain risks and improving overall operation efficiency.

1.2 Research Objectives

Building upon the introduction above, the following outlines the specific objectives of this research:

Firstly, this study intends to perform an exhaustive examination and comparison of five quantized LLMs - namely, Zephyr 7b-alpha, Llama-2-7b, Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 (a high-quality Sparse Mixture of Experts model (SMoE) with open weights), Microsoft's Phi-2 (with 2.7 billion parameters), and Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1 - in handling supply chain risk data within resource-constrained environments. Specifically, we aim to evaluate the relative merits and weaknesses of each LLM in terms of accuracy, scalability, adaptability to varying degrees of resource availability and most importantly, Inference quality.

Secondly, this research endeavors to investigate the implications of deploying these LLMs via WasmEdge/Web Assembly, as compared to conventional Python deployment. We hypothesize that such alternative approaches may yield improvements in performance metrics such as inference quality, inference time, resource utilization, and computational efficiency. Moreover, we aim to establish empirical evidence substantiating the extent of these potential gains, and to highlight the underlying factors contributing to any observed differences.

Lastly, this study seeks to identify optimal configurations for deploying LLMs in small business settings, guided by the principle of "doing more with less." Specifically, we aim to pinpoint the most effective strategies for balancing computational trade-offs in such environments, taking into account factors such as hardware compatibility, power consumption, and ease of integration. Through these processes, we hope to explore previously underexplored dimensions of LLM deployment.

1.3 Scope of the Study

This study will undertake a thorough exploration of several vital performance indicators related to quantized LLMs, encompassing inference time, resource utilization (including GPU VRAM and system RAM), and computational efficiency (measured by branches, instructions, and misses). Additionally, the research will examine the influence of varying quantization levels and model parameters on inference quality and runtime performance. By concentrating on these pivotal elements, this study aims to furnish valuable insights into the delicate balance between model complexity, quantization fidelity, and overall performance in resource-constrained conditions. In

doing so, it hopes to offer practical guidance for navigating the trade-offs inherent in selecting appropriate LLMs for small business settings.

1.4 Thesis Structure

The thesis will be structured in a systematic manner, comprising several sections to ensure a coherent presentation of the research findings. These sections will include an introduction to the research topic, a comprehensive literature review, a detailed methodology outlining the experimental setup and data collection procedures, an in-depth performance analysis of the quantized LLMs, a case study exploring their application in small business supply chain risk management, a discussion on the limitations of the study, and finally, conclusions and recommendations for future research endeavors.

2 Definitions

This section sets forth the key terms and concepts integral to understanding the study, establishing a conceptual foundation for subsequent chapters.

2.1 Quantized Language Models (LLMs)

At the heart of this research lies the concept of quantized language models (LLMs). Quantization is a technique that reduces the precision of a model's weights from floating-point to fixed-point representations. This transformation results in smaller model sizes and faster inference times, making them more suited for deployment in resource-constrained environments. (Liu et al., 2024) Fixed-point representations typically use fewer bits than floating-point, resulting in reduced memory footprint and arithmetic intensity, consequently lowering energy consumption and latency.

However, the trade-off for smaller models and quicker inference comes at the expense of potentially degraded inference quality. The loss in precision caused by quantization might result in lower accuracy compared to their full-precision counterparts. Nevertheless, researchers have developed novel techniques to maintain inference quality despite quantization. One such method is layerwise quantization, which applies varying precisions to layers depending on their sensitivity to quantization error. Another promising direction is mixed-precision quantization, which dynamically selects the optimum precision for each layer during inference.

2.2 Resource-Constrained Computing Environments

Resource-constrained computing environments refer to systems whose computational resources, e.g., memory, CPU cycles, or power, are severely limited. This limitation impacts their capacity to execute complex computational tasks efficiently. Mobile devices, IoT gadgets, and embedded systems exemplify typical resource-constrained environments. These devices usually possess scant memory, limited processing power, and constrained energy reserves, restricting their ability to carry out computation-intensive tasks demanded by large-scale language models. (Bai et al., 2024)

Running state-of-the-art language models in resource-constrained environments is challenging due to their considerable memory footprints and extensive computational requirements. (Z. Liu et al., 2023) Modern LLMs contain billions of parameters, consuming vast amounts of memory and computational resources. When deployed in resource-constrained environments, these

models encounter issues such as thrashing, excessive page faults, and long inference times that affect user experience. It is important that efficient methods similar to that explored by (Hong et al., 2024) are developed to deploy quantized LLMs in such settings without jeopardizing inference quality.

2.3 Wasmedge/WebAssembly Deployment

WebAssembly (WASM) is a binary instruction format that permits compilation of code written in multiple languages into a bytecode format executable by contemporary web browsers. Wasmedge represents a lightweight, high-performance runtime engine for WASM, compatible with numerous backends, including Linux, Windows, macOS, Android, iOS, and various other POSIX-compliant systems. Wasmedge brings WASM closer to edge computing and IoT devices by adding extensions for file system access, networking, and multithreading, amongst other functionalities.(WasmEdge, n.d.)

Employing Wasmedge/WebAssembly for deploying quantized LLMs offers several benefits. First, it abstracts away platform-specific concerns, facilitating portability across a plethora of devices, irrespective of their underlying hardware architecture. Second, Wasmedge/WebAssembly enables just-in-time (JIT) compilation, translating the bytecode to machine-native instructions during runtime, thus reducing cold-start latencies. Wasmedge/WebAssembly ensures strong isolation properties, safeguarding against malicious attacks and vulnerabilities stemming from shared resources.

2.4 Large Language Models (LLM) deployed in this project

Below, we outline the details, structure and use cases for each model we used in the thesis.

2.4.1 Zephyr 7b-alpha

Zephyr 7b-alpha is a quantized variant of Zephyr series of language models. It is the first in a series of such models that is specifically fine-tuned from Mistralai/Mistral-7B-v0.1 and trained on publicly available datasets, including synthetic datasets. This quantized comprises approximately 7 billion parameters, placing it near the upper bound of currently attainable language models. Its authors claim that its intended use is for chats, since it was fine-tuned on UltraChat dataset with a wide range of synthetic dialogues generated by ChatGPT.

The authors claim that this model has not been trained to prioritize human preferences, which could lead to problematic outputs (as seen in chapter 5, where this model refused to return inference in the Python experiments) when prompted in certain ways. It might also display some bias, because the training data for Zephyr-7B-alpha was unknown, but likely included some web data and technical sources. This could be a potential source of bias which could lead to defective and skewed output from the model. This is a factor to take into consideration in its use. (HuggingFaceH4/Zephyr-7b-alpha · Hugging Face, 2001)

2.4.2 Llama-2-7b-Chat

Llama-2-7b-chat is an example of a quantized LLM, originating from Meta's language modeling initiatives. Similar to Zephyr 7b-alpha, this version has 7 billion parameters. The base model Llama 2 has a collection of fine-tuned and pretrained generative text models, from 7 to 70 billion parameters. 7B's finetuning is optimized for dialogue use cases. The authors claim that its Llama-2-Chat models outperform open-source chat models on most benchmarks they tested. The tuned versions use supervised fine-tuning (SFT) as well as reinforcement learning with human feedback (RLHF) to execute human prompts. Meta claims that the base mode from which the quantized versions originate was pretrained on 2 trillion tokens of data from publicly sources. (Meta-llama/Llama-2-7b-chat-hf · Hugging Face, n.d.)

2.4.3 Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1

Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 is a Mixture of Experts (MoE) model with a sparse architecture. MoEs are a type of architecture where a subset of 'experts' is conditionally activated based on the input.(Mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 · Hugging Face, n.d.) Mixtral-8x7B contains 7 billion trainable parameters distributed across 8 expert groups, totaling 46.7 billion activatable units. (Sanseviero et al., 2023)

Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 produces exceptional results, producing coherent text that surpasses that of other models.

2.4.4 Microsoft's Phi-2

Phi-2 is a lightweight model created by Microsoft. Its authors claim that It comes with 2.7 billion parameters and is trained with several NLP synthetic texts and filtered websites. They also claim that it was not fine-tuned through reinforment learning, that is, from human feedback. Its repository clearly states that it was only created to provide a resource for researchers with a

non-restricted small model for exploration of details like societal bias, toxicity, safety challenges. They also state that Phi-2 is best suited for Question & Answer formats, chat formats and code formats. This means that it is not suited for Instruction-based tasks. It is inadequate for production-level usage. (Microsoft/Phi-2 · Hugging Face, n.d.) In this project we will make use of a quantized version of this model that comes in a GGUF format.

2.4.5 Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1

Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1 is a model based on Mistral-7B-V0.1, but modified to for instruction-based tasks. It was encoded within 7 billion parameters, using training data obtained from publicly available sources. The authors claim that since it is an instruct-based transformer model built from Mistral-7B-v0.1, with features such as group-query attention, sliding-window attention, and byte-fallback BPE tokenizer.(Mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1 · Hugging Face, n.d.) They also warn about some of its limitations include and absence of moderation mechanisms. Hence it lacks guardrails for moderating outputs. These details must be put into consideration in evaluating the results from these models.

2.5 Performance Metrics

Using quantized LLMs requires close observation of its performance metrics, such as task clock, inference time, resource utilization, and all other computational indices. Monitoring resource utilization can help us know how the model is respond to setup constraints and instructions given to it. Below, we list out key indices that were monitored during this experimentation.

2.5.1 Task Clock (msec)

The task clock metric records the amount of time spent executing tasks in milliseconds. Monitoring this value helps measure the overall efficiency of the system. It can also help us to identify bottlenecks causing delays in completing tasks. Comparing the task clock measurements across different LLMs can show us which models execute tasks more quickly and efficiently. With this, we can optimize them better.

2.5.1.1 Context Switches

Context switching in computers happen when processors switch from executing one process or thread to another, i.e. saving and restoring the previous context in order to allow the next one to resume execution. Tracking context switch events is important since frequent switches can introduce overhead and cause a drop in performance. Monitoring the frequency of context

switches in processes initiated by our quantized models can help us know how smoothly each LLM handles simultaneous tasks and threads, guiding efforts toward streamlined execution. Hence, the fewer the switches, the more optimized the process, and the higher the switches, the higher the potential overhead that could affect performance.

2.5.1.2 CPU Migrations

CPU (Central Processing Unit) migrations normally happen when a process that is running on the computer moves between logical CPUs, sometimes triggered by the kernel attempting to distribute workloads equally among CPUs. Investigating CPU migration frequencies can expose potential sources of slowdowns, as moving processes between CPUs adds overhead and interrupts smooth execution. This is a factor to keep an eye on. Hence, assessing LLMs based on CPU migration counts can highlight the most stable and consistent models in terms of CPU usage.

2.5.1.3 Page Faults (millions)

Page faults can happen when a program tries to access a memory location that was not mapped to physical memory. This absence triggers the operating system to move pages between physical memory and secondary storage. Recording page fault occurrences can tell us whether there are potential reliability issues in memory management, or potential memory leaks. Evaluating LLMs based on their respective page fault counts can help researchers know the most memory-efficient models, by identifying those that allocate memory intelligently and release unused resources timely.

2.5.1.4 Cycles (trillions)

When we track the number of processor cycles executed by the LLMs, this can shed light on the computational load that is demanded by each model. Analyzing this metric can expose issues in the load demands of different LLMs, identifying models that consume a lot of resources or only a little. Benchmarking LLMs using cycle counts can aid in recognizing the least resource-intensive alternatives.

2.5.1.5 Instructions (trillions)

Since this research is interested in ways to run models in resource-constrained setups, then monitoring the number of instructions processed by each LLM is essential to help us know what

demand these models put on the computer. Observing the differences in instruction counts can help us to know how powerful the models are.

2.5.1.6 Branches (billions)

Counting the number of branches created by processes initiated by LLMs are an important factor in tracking the performance of a model. It can help us speculate about how deep the model's logical operations are going. High number of branches can indicate models with a superior ability in reasoning and inferencing.

2.5.1.7 Branch Misses (millions)

Examining branch misses—instances where a predicted branch path differs from reality—can indicate the accuracy of each LLM's internal decision-making apparatus. The bigger the branch misses, the less efficient a model is in the way it demands from the processors. This is a factor to look closely at.

2.5.2 Time Elapsed (seconds)

Recording the elapsed time from initiating model loading until completion indicates the wall-clock time required by each LLM to perform its duties.

2.5.2.1 User Time (seconds)

Distinguishing between user and system time allows researchers to observe how much time the LLMs spend actively processing tasks compared to waiting for external resources. Focusing solely on user time excludes idle periods, thereby, pointing to the true computational load exerted or demanded by each LLM.

2.5.2.2 Sys Time (seconds)

'Sys Time' accounts for the portion of LLM execution that goes to system calls, measuring how much time LLMs spend interacting with the operating system rather than calculating outcomes. Isolating sys time can help researchers to know how dependent each LLM is on the Operating System (OS) for assistance, thereby, exposing us to models that rely too heavily on external resources.

2.5.3 Prompt Context Size

Evaluating LLMs based on prompt context size can show how sensitive each model is to the length of input strings. When we monitor how this value affects the LLMs inference, the users can better understand how much history and background information each LLM accepts easily. Sorting LLMs by their prompt context sizes can show those that tolerate bigger input.

2.5.3.1 Number of Tokens to Predict

Determining the number of tokens produced by each LLM can shed light on the scope of each model's predictive abilities. Counting token generations in LLMs can tell us those that excel at generating longer threads.

2.5.3.2 Number of Layers to Run on the GPU

Establishing the precise number of layers devoted to the GPU for each LLM can demonstrate how each model handles parallel processing and offloads computations from the CPU. Models that are capable of taking bigger values without crashing from memory errors, might be good candidates to consider.

2.5.3.3 Batch Size for Prompt Processing

Specifying batch sizes for prompt processing can tell us how an LLM scales. It shows how easily a model can accommodate massive submissions. We can make fair comparisons by attempting to standardize batch sizes across LLMs.

3 Literature Review

This chapter documents significant leaps in developments surrounding natural language processing through advances in large language models (LLMs) utilizing architectures like Transformers. It then gives details about light-weight AI language models and their capacities when being deployed in resource-constrained ecosystems.

3.1 General Overview of Large Language Models (LLM) In Resource-Constrained Environments

The emergence of large language models (LLMs) can be traced back to the groundbreaking work titled 'Attention Is All You Need,' published in 2017 by Ashish Vaswani and his colleagues. (Vaswani et al., 2023) This pioneering research introduced the concept of Transformers, revolutionizing the way we process sequential information. Instead of employing traditional recurrent layers, the authors replaced them with self-attention mechanisms—enabling efficient handling of complex relationships between elements present within input sequences without sacrificing computation speed. As opposed to recurrence-based approaches, Transformers offered enhanced parallelism capabilities, with parallelism being a distinguishing property of it (Sanford et al., 2024). This significant capability for parallelism accelerates training times substantially. Following the inception of Transformers, two subsequent studies significantly contributed to advancing the developments of LLMs. Firstly, Transformer XL was unveiled in 2019 by (Dai et al., 2019), building on the foundation laid out by Attention Is All You Need. This novel variant extended the context window beyond fixed lengths, enabling better comprehension of intricate linguistic structures spanning more extensive stretches of text. By mitigating constraints imposed by limited context windows, Transformer XL facilitated improved modeling of long-range dependencies inherent in natural language discourse. Simultaneously, another major milestone came in the same year - BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers).

Unlike prior models focusing predominantly on autoregressive generation, BERT emphasized bidirectional representations acquired via pre-training tasks encompassing both masked language modeling and next-sentence prediction objectives (Devlin et al., 2018). BERT went on to achieve remarkable results that surpassed preceding systems across multiple benchmarks pertinent to natural language understanding tasks. After BERT, followed the RoBERTa model,

which served as a refined extension of BERT, which worked by eliminating the ‘next-sentence prediction objective’, implementing dynamic masking patterns, and increasing batch sizes during optimization, (Liu et al., 2019) RoBERTa successfully amplified the proficiency exhibited by its predecessor.

The rapid expansion of large language models (LLMs) led researchers to explore solutions tailored for resource-constrained environments, which necessitate compact AI models operating in low-memory footprints and consuming less power (Bai et al., 2024). These settings impose challenges relating to hardware limitations. Developers seek to create lightweight AI models that retain acceptable accuracy levels while featuring minimal size, quick runtime speeds, and low energy demands. Multiple optimization strategies have been employed to tackle these challenges. Reducing model parameters, quantizing full-precision weights into lower bit-width values, pruning less important connections, and compressing network architectures via knowledge distillation are common tactics.

WasmEdge is a promising solution for executing WebAssembly modules outside browsers, and more recently, also enabling LLMs to function in resource-constrained settings like mobile devices and embedded systems. This capability extends the reach of LLMs beyond conventional computing platforms and ventures into edge computing. Addressing resource-constrained environments requires understanding underlying challenges and developing highly optimized algorithms capable of functioning efficiently within strict bounds.

3.2 Quantized language models in resource-constrained environments & related publications.

Quantized language models represent the model parameters using fewer bits, reducing memory usage and computational costs without significantly hindering performance (Han et al., 2015). LLMs are powerful, but tend to require a lot of computing power, making them difficult to use on devices with limited resources. Quantization reduces the amount of data needed to store the model, with minimal impact on performance. There are various quantization techniques, each with its strengths, weaknesses, and consequences on model performance.

One type of quantization is post-training static quantization, which includes linear uniform quantization and logarithmic quantization. Linear uniform quantization divides the range of parameter values into equally sized bins and maps each value to the nearest bin center (Krishnamoorthi, 2018). In this straightforward method, capturing distribution of weights for models with large dynamic range is not so effective. In contrast, logarithmic quantization is more efficient. It works by scaling the parameter values geometrically, and then allocating more bits to smaller absolute values and fewer bits to larger ones (Anderson et al., 2018). Although logarithmic quantization allows for a smoother approximation, especially for small weights, it tends to perform worse than linear uniform quantization when the distribution of weights is symmetrical (Nahshan et al., 2019).

On the same level with post-training static quantization, we have the dynamic quantization method, which is another category of quantization, that adaptively changes the scale factor according to the statistics of the activations in each layer. During runtime, the scale factor enables mapping the activations to the closest representative value within a specified range (Micikevicius et al., 2017). Dynamic quantization improves the overall performance of the quantized model, although it increases computational complexity during inference.

These methods are well documented by several researchers. For example, (Jin et al., 2024) investigated a technique that uses quantization to improve the efficiency of LLMs. They studied different ways in which quantization might affect LLMs, including how they learn and perform tasks, how they align with their training data, and how efficiently they manage memory and speed. The results showed that using 4-bit quantization with LLMs can maintain performance close to un-quantized models and larger quantized models can even outperform smaller ones. They note that quantization can slow down the model, and that there is a need for further research to level out the benefits of reduced memory usage with faster processing speeds for quantized LLMs. Jin et al. (2024) further recommended that development efforts should be devoted to address the inference speed tradeoffs associated with memory consumption in quantized LLMs.

In a different research, (Xiao et al., 2022) explored a method called SmoothQuant, to improve the efficiency of LLMs after they are trained (post-training). As existing techniques for reducing data storage (quantization) often struggle to balance these goals, SmoothQuant addresses this by focusing on a specific challenge, namely; activations in the LLM being harder to compress than weights. They presented a solution that involved mathematically transforming the model to make compressing activations easier, while they kept the overall function unchanged. This

method works by compressing both weights and activations to 8 bits (INT8) for various LLM architectures. Xiao et al., reported improvements in speed (up to 1.56 times faster) and memory usage (up to 2 times less) with minimal impact on accuracy. This efficiency gain allowed the researchers to run a very large LLM (530 billion parameters) on a single machine, which was previously not possible. A concrete take-away of this research was that SmoothQuant offered a practical solution to reduce the hardware needed for LLMs, making them more accessible and affordable to users.

In an earlier research, (Wang et al., 2019) had experimented with the Hardware-Aware Automated Quantization (HAQ) technique, as a way to improve the efficiency of deep neural networks (DNNs) for specific hardware. Traditionally, this fine-tuning involves manually finding the best balance between factors like speed, energy use, and model size for each layer of the DNN. This is difficult and time-consuming. HAQ automates this process using reinforcement learning. It takes into account feedback from a hardware simulator to directly measure factors like speed and energy use. This allows HAQ to find the best bitwidth (number of bits used to store data) for each layer, considering both the DNN architecture and the specific hardware it will run on. Compared to traditional methods, HAQ can significantly improve speed (1.4-1.95 times faster) and energy efficiency (1.9 times less) with minimal impact on accuracy. HAQ reveals that the optimal settings for different hardware (like powerful cloud servers vs. mobile devices) are very different. This technique was proposed as a possible solution for designing DNNs and hardware accelerators.

Likewise, (Ashfaq et al., 2022) experimented on ways to speed up deep learning models on devices fitted with ARM processors (edge devices similar to mobile phones). The authors proposed two techniques: Deeplite Neutrino (for optimizing models) and Deeplite Runtime (for running the models on devices). They also used a special technique called ultra-low bit quantization to further reduce the size and processing needs of the models. Their proposed methods were designed to work on a wide range of ARM devices, both 32-bit and 64-bit. They reported performance improvements of up to 5 times faster in comparison to other existing tools for running deep learning models. This proposed technique could help improve the performance of deep learning models on mobile devices, since they tend to require a lot of computing power.

3.3 Review of literature related to AI solutions in supply chain risk management (SCRM)

Supply chain disruptions can cause severe consequences for businesses, ranging from increased operational costs to reputational damage (Hosseini et al., 2019). Organizations increasingly turn to Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions to mitigate and manage risks in their supply chains. Several AI techniques are currently utilized in supply chain risk management, such as forecasting, anomaly detection, simulation, and optimization.

Before the advent of LLMs, some organizations made use of fuzzy systems in supply chain analysis software. (Đurić et al., 2019) proposed a model for managing risk in production supply chains. They focused on both economic and social factors alongside common operational and organizational ones. The model used fuzzy logic to account for the inherent uncertainty in risk assessment. Decision-makers provide their judgment on the severity and frequency of potential risk factors. Fuzzy set theory and fuzzy analytical hierarchy process (FAHP) were then used to analyze this information and determine the overall risk level for the supply chain. The authors specifically mention the application of this model to the automotive industry, with a goal to identify weak points in the supply chain and propose appropriate actions to reduce or eliminate supply chain risk.

Similar fuzzy logic techniques were increasingly used together with traditional Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) for tasks like evaluating agricultural risk management. Traditional FMEAs are a method that uses three factors to prioritize risk, namely: severity, occurrence and detectability. This method had its limitations, such as inability to consider the varying impacts of severity on different aspects (cost, time, quality). For example, (Zandi et al., 2020) attempted to address limitations in managing risks for agricultural projects by improving FMEA. They did this by introducing a “Hybrid-FMEA” that combined FMEA with fuzzy TOPSIS and AHP (analytical methods). This allowed for more flexibility by letting users adjust the importance of different risk factors. Their findings demonstrated that this approach could effectively prioritize risks in agriculture, highlighting water/energy supply, and pest control as the most critical. This research was the first to combine an extended FMEA with multi-criteria decision making for agricultural risk management.

Chu et al. (2020) proposed a framework for managing global supply chains, by using text analysis from two sources: academic papers and online news articles. The technique analyzes academic papers on the topic of global supply chain, using methods such as term frequency, correlation analysis, and bi-gram analysis, to identify important risk factors. Topic modeling is then used to categorize these factors into seven main risk types, then they use sentiment analysis on news articles to understand how the level of these risks varies across different regions

Schroeder and Lodemann (2021) identified a scarcity of well-documented examples in existence that showcased how machine learning was applied in SCRM. Lamenting that this area was promising, but under-documented.. They noted how detailed information about its implementation was lacking in scientific literature. They noted that available examples tended to mostly highlight the use of ML for early detection of risks in production, transportation, and supply chain as a whole. It concluded by emphasizing a dire need for further research to fully comprehend the potential of ML in SCRM. This includes developing methods to assess its effectiveness, and establishing better knowledge sharing between companies and researchers.

In more recent times, (M. B. Shishehgarkhaneh et al., 2024) investigated how different transformer models (BERT, RoBERTa, etc.) can be used to identify important details (Named Entity Recognition - NER) from news articles related to volatile and complex construction supply chain risks in Australia. The study discovered that RoBERTa performed the best, though all the models they tested were able to effectively identify these important details. It showed that NLP (Natural Language Processing) techniques like NER can be useful for improving SCRM in construction, especially in australia.

Another noteworthy review was conducted by (Kosasih et al., 2023) investigated the potentials of neuro-symbolic AI (combining neural networks and symbolic reasoning) to enhance explainability in supply chain management (SCM) AI models. The paper conducted a systematic review that identified a focus on a limited range of neuro-symbolic techniques, primarily Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS) Models, for applications like supplier selection and demand forecasting. The researchers identified a gap in exploring newer techniques like graph neural networks, etc. It then concluded by proposing further research in five key areas, including: development of new methods to make AI models in SCM more understandable for decision-making, utilizing knowledge graphs to model complex supply chain data relationships, exploring methods to handle unstructured data (images, graphs, text), integrating existing domain knowledges to reduce data requirements and bias in AI models, and investigating ways

to make AI models to learn from learning itself and combine different learning/reasoning approaches.

Srivastava et al. (2024) also explored the use of LLMs to improve supply chain management. They used data triangulation (combining information from 33 published academic works that provided theoretical foundations on LLMs and supply chain management, as well as a massive dataset of 3421 social media documents that included tweets, industry reports, expert opinions and social media posts. Then they proceeded to analyze this data by using BERT models (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) to extract key themes and insights from the data. The research discovered four key areas where LLMs can offer significant benefits, namely: optimizing supply chains, managing risks and security, improving knowledge management, and automating contract analysis.

3.4 Conclusion of literature review and research approach

In conclusion, this literature review has attempted to show that there is an alarming paucity of scientific papers on LLMs in SCRM. Our research aims to contribute to filling this gap by exploring the use of LLMs in solving supply chain problems, particularly in resource-restrained setups. Anticipating the potential computational and cost challenges that may be faced by small enterprises in SCRM, this research seeks to identify optimal scenarios for deploying and managing LLMs in resource-constrained environments. In response to the challenges posed by resource-constrained environments, researchers have devoted efforts to creating lightweight AI models that minimize computational overhead and memory usage while maintaining acceptable accuracy levels. Various optimization strategies, such as reducing model parameters, quantization techniques, and pruning less important connections, have proven beneficial in this regard. Also, the literature review has revealed that AI solutions have become increasingly integral to supply chain risk management (SCRM). Techniques such as forecasting, anomaly detection, simulation, and optimization have played significant roles in mitigating and managing risks in supply chains. Prior to the rise of LLMs, fuzzy logic systems and extensions to Traditional Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) were employed to address risk management issues. Recently, however, there has been a shift towards more sophisticated AI techniques, including text analysis and machine learning applications in SCRM.

Despite these advancements, there is still a recognized scarcity of well-documented examples showcasing the application of machine learning in SCRM. Detailed information about

implementation and effectiveness assessment is lacking, leaving room for further research. Newer techniques such as neuro-symbolic AI and graph neural networks have yet to be thoroughly explored in the context of supply chain management. Addressing the need to improve explainability in AI models and handling unstructured data like images, graphs, and texts are promising areas for future investigation.

This research intends to capitalize on the potential of LLMs in solving supply chain problems, taking into account the unique challenges encountered in resource-constrained environments. By identifying optimal scenarios for deploying and managing LLMs in such settings, we hope to contribute meaningful insights to the fields of AI and SCRM. This presents the potential to benefit small enterprises that will increasingly face computational and cost challenges in SCRM analysis.

3.4.1 Research Design and Approach

The research approach section outlines the methodological used to achieve the study's objectives. It details the experimental design, data collection procedures, and analytical techniques utilized to investigate the performance of quantized language models in resource-constrained environments.

3.4.1.1 Comparative Analysis Approach

This research will apply a comparative analysis approach to thoroughly evaluate the performance of five selected quantized LLMs (Language Learning Models) in supply chain data analysis. The comparative analysis approach is an effective methodology for comparing and contrasting objects, entities, or phenomena based on their attributes, characteristics, or performances. This approach enables researchers to draw useful conclusions on the relative performance of different LLMs across various deployment platforms.

The rationale behind adopting a comparative analysis approach is to ensure that the research provides a broad overview on the performance of the selected LLMs, enabling decision-makers to choose the most appropriate LLM based on their unique requirements, preferences, and constraints. Given the abundance of LLMs available and deployment platforms, a comparative analysis approach is essential to provide a balanced assessment of their performance.

3.4.1.2 Key Characteristics of the Comparative Analysis Approach

Three main characteristics define the proposed comparative analysis approach, namely:

- a. **Empirical Evidence:** The approach relies on empirical evidence obtained from carefully planned and conducted experiments. This evidence forms the foundations of the comparative analysis, providing a basis for valid conclusions on the relative performance of the LLMs.
- b. **Controlled Conditions:** All experiments will be carried out under controlled conditions to minimize error and ensure that the recorded observations reflect the performance of the LLMs.

- c. **Robust Analytical Techniques:** Solid analytical techniques will be employed to derive insights from the collated data. Rigour in our calculations will be essential to prevent question on credibility of the outcomes or methods of analysis.

3.4.1.3 Benefits of the Comparative Analysis Approach

Adopting a comparative analysis approach offers several advantages. Some key advantages include insights, validation of authors claims by comparing the models side-by-side, as well as achieve some basic performance benchmarks that can be used by a broader audience.. This method allows for a broad application of our findings to other fields that find it relevant. For example, when we evaluate LLMs in a comparative way, it opens up insights into the performance differences between the models. This allows us to verify the claims of the authors.

3.4.1.4 Limitations of the Comparative Analysis Approach

Although comparative analysis offers many benefits, it also presents some worth noting. These limitations include complexity, cost burdens and time-consumption. The cost can be high due to the need for capable hardware, tools for monitoring and complex means of acquiring the data, all of which can present issues with cost and time. It is essential that researchers weigh the advantages and possible drawbacks of these challenges before making comparative analysis the method of choice on a project like this.

3.4.1.5 Addressing Limitations

Despite the acknowledged limitations, the author of this publication has taken sufficient measures to address these concerns. For instance, to tackle the complexity problem, the author had to get sufficient acquaintance on requisite expertise in LLMs, supply chain data analysis, and deployment platforms. Regarding the cost concern, leasing of unavailable hardware was the most viable option. With respect to time savings, all experimental phases were carefully scheduled to optimize time and available hardware resources.

3.4.2 Data Collection Procedures

This section outlines the systematic procedures undertaken to gather relevant supply chain risk datasets and configure experimental environments. To ensure a systematic and accurate collection of data for evaluating the performance of various quantized LLMs (Language Learning Models) in supply chain data analysis, the following procedures were implemented:

Step 1: Selection and preparation of supply chain risk datasets

The initial stage of data collection involved sourcing relevant supply chain risk data from publicly available sources to be used as input for the LLMs. Datasets consisting of risk reports and supply chain news acquired from public sources. Once gathered, some parts of these datasets had to be cleaned and preprocessed to remove unnecessary white spaces, advertisements and images. Following this, the final data was saved in .TXT file formats to ensure compatibility with the LLMs and facilitate easy integration during the experimental phase. Each dataset will be a maximum of 1069 words of supply chain text only.

Step 2: Setting up experimental environments

Next, experimental setups were put together for each LLM under consideration, with predefined hardware resources allocated to simulate possible resource-constraints that might be encountered in small business settings. Using a Linux Ubuntu 22.04 Jammy LTS on an ACER Predator Helios 300 laptop equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1065 GPU (6GB VRAM), 32GB system RAM, and ample disk space guaranteed consistent evaluation conditions for all LLMs. This allowed us carry out an unbiased comparison of all LLMs based on their performance alone.

Step 3: Configuring LLMs for testing

Once the experimental environments were prepared, the quantized LLMs were loaded and initialized within these settings. Both WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp versions of the LLMs were installed and tested to ensure proper functionality and compatibility with the limited hardware resources.

Step 4: Execution of LLMs and monitoring performance

Each LLM was subsequently executed multiple times (five (5) times each), feeding it identical supply chain risk datasets (of 1069-word chunks per runtime) to ensure a fair and consistent

assessment of performance. Throughout the testing period, advanced monitoring tools such as Perf tools (Brendangregg, n.d.), Glances (Nicolargo, n.d.), and custom scripts were employed to gather performance metrics relating to GPU and RAM usage.

Perf tools is a Linux-based performance analysis toolset that was extensively used in this research for recording event counters and hardware performance statistics. Simultaneously, Glances, a cross-platform system monitoring utility, delivered live, detailed views of the experimental environments, including temperature readouts, fan speeds, and uptime statuses.

Custom Bash scripts and NVIDIA's `nvidia-smi` software were tailored to monitor GPU and RAM usage further supplemented the monitoring toolkit. Written in Bash, these scripts helped to capture real-time snapshots of GPU utilization, memory utilization, and power draw percentages, as well as RAM allocation breakdowns, buffered memory, cached memory, and available buffer pools. Together, these monitoring tools allowed the author to capture several performance metrics, that ensured that the experiments can provide thorough and accurate representation of each LLM's abilities under resource-constrained conditions.

Step 5: Storage and aggregation of collected data

Following the successful execution of each LLM and the collection of relevant performance metrics, the raw data was stored in secure, locally managed databases. Upon conclusion of the testing phase, the data was then extracted and consolidated, forming the foundation for further analysis and interpretation. This data collection procedures formed a comprehensive and systematic approach to obtaining and organizing the necessary data for evaluating the performance of quantized LLMs within supply chain risk analysis. Utilizing advanced monitoring tools and custom scripts, performance metrics were collected and documented.

3.4.3 Performance Metrics and Measurement Tools

To evaluate the performance of the quantized LLMs in supply chain data analysis, an ideal set of performance metrics were identified, and measurement tools were selected to obtain accurate and reliable data. The chosen performance metrics fall under three main categories: inference quality, computational efficiency, and resource utilization.

3.4.3.1 Inference Quality Metrics

Inference quality is a critical factor for evaluating the effectiveness of LLMs. To assess the inference quality of the quantized LLMs, nine (9) evaluation criteria were identified and rated on a five-point Likert scale. These ratings serve as a valuable indicator of each model's performance, enabling a comprehensive comparison of their inference capabilities. The evaluation criteria include:

1. **Relevance to prompt:** Measures how well the generated text aligns with the given input prompt. Ratings range from 1 (very poor) to 5 (excellent).
2. **Coherence & Flow:** Assesses the smooth transitions between ideas and the overall coherence of the generated text. Ratings range from 1 (very poor) to 5 (excellent).
3. **General Accuracy:** Evaluates the truthfulness and factual correspondence of the generated text. Ratings range from 1 (inaccurate) to 5 (highly accurate).
4. **Erroneous Responses on Unknown Prompts:** Measures the tendency of the model to produce incorrect or nonsensical responses when dealing with unfamiliar input prompts. Ratings range from 1 (extremely erroneous) to 5 (not erroneous).
5. **Fluency:** Assesses the ease with which the generated text flows and reads naturally. Ratings range from 1 (disfluent) to 5 (highly fluent).
6. **Insight:** Evaluates the depth of understanding demonstrated by the generated text. Ratings range from 1 (no insight) to 5 (deep insight).
7. **Specificity:** Measures how precisely the output addresses specific details mentioned in the input prompt rather than providing generic statements.
8. **Understandability:** Evaluates the clarity of expression, making it easy for non-domain experts to comprehend the key points.
9. **Tone of Cautiousness:** Assesses the level of caution expressed in the generated text, which ranges from 1 (certainty & confidence) to 5 (cautious & noncommittal).
10. **Completeness and consistency:** The completeness and consistency criterion, measures the degree to which the generated text remains consistent throughout,

especially when generating long responses or multiple related pieces of information.

These evaluation criteria allows us to quantitatively assess the inference quality of the quantized LLMs. By doing this, we can gain insights into each model's ability to generate meaningful, accurate, and coherent responses to a diverse range of input prompts under our resource-constrained setups.

3.4.3.2 Computational Efficiency Metrics

Computational efficiency is important for deploying LLMs in resource-constrained environments. The following metrics were chosen to evaluate the computational performance of the LLMs:

1. **Inference time:** The time taken by the LLM to generate output based on the given input prompt. Faster inference time can often imply better computational efficiency.
2. **Operations per second (OPS):** OPS Indicates the number of operations the LLM can perform within a unit of time. Increased OPS signifies higher computational efficiency.
3. **Energy consumption:** The amount of electrical power required for LLM operations. Lesser energy consumption leads to lower operating costs and possible low carbon footprints.

3.4.3.3 Resource Utilization Metrics

Resource utilization is very important in measuring the optimization and load exerted or demand by LLMs in resource-constrained environments. The following metrics were selected to estimate the resource utilization of the LLMs:

1. **GPU VRAM consumption:** This metric measures the exact amount of GPU memory (VRAM) used by the LLM during operations. Low VRAM consumption leaves more resources available for other applications and improves overall system stability. While high GPU VRAM might affect the completion and speed of inference of the LLMs.
2. **System RAM consumption:** This metric tracks the amount of physical system random access memory (RAM) used by the LLM. Less RAM consumption enables smoother multitasking and prevents system slowdowns.
3. **Power draw (%):** Monitors the percentage of maximum and minimum power drawn during LLM operations. Lower power draw means lower energy bills.

3.4.3.4 Measurement Tools

To collect the performance metrics mentioned above, a combination of advanced monitoring tools and custom scripts were used. Specifically, Perf tools, Glances, and custom scripts tailored to monitor GPU and RAM usage were employed.

1. **Perf tools:** These Linux-based performance analysis tools provide detailed event counters and hardware performance statistics that tell the researcher the level of computational efficiency and resource utilization of the LLMs. (Brendangregg, n.d.)
2. **Glances:** As mentioned earlier, this tool is a cross-platform system monitoring utility, that gives real-time and detailed views of the experimental environments, including temperature readouts, fan speeds, and uptime statuses. (Nicolargo, n.d.)
3. **Custom scripts:** Created in Bash, these scripts captured real-time snapshots of GPU utilization, memory utilization, and power draw percentages, as well as RAM allocation breakdowns and others.

3.4.4 Experimental Setup and Hardware Configuration

Our experimental setup consists of a deliberately configured Linux Ubuntu 22.04 Jammy LTS laptop, equipped with an older NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1065 Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) with six (6GB) gigabytes of GPU VRAM. This choice of hardware emphasizes the resource-constrained scenario, with conditions faced by smaller users and individuals with limited computational resources, who cannot afford cloud computing. The GTX 1065 is an older generation GPU compared to the newer RTX 2000 - 5000 series, and the VRAM allocation of 6GB falls short of the more recent 12GB to 15GB configurations seen in modern GPUs. By intentionally employing this setup, we aim to challenge the performance of the quantized LLMs under relatively strained conditions. In addition to the details above, we had installed 32GB of system Random Access Memory (RAM) and a Solid State Drive (SSD) with 100GB disk space.

We also chose Linux Ubuntu 22.04 Jammy LTS as the operating system due to its stability and versatility. Linux grants immediate command line access to low-level operations of the operating system, which is beneficial for monitoring or extracting performance metrics needed. In contrast, other operating systems, such as Windows, can be more cumbersome when it comes to acquiring such data.

As part of our experimental setup, we test the LLMs using the Python/LLaMA.cpp versus Wasmedge (for WebAssembly) deployment platform. Wasmedge operates without issues in Linux environments, allowing us to package the LLMs as WebAssembly modules and run them across various platforms, including web browsers and containerized applications like Docker and WASM cloud.

With this limited setup, we hope to stretch the limits of the quantized LLMs in order to be able to benchmark their performance capabilities within these constraints.

3.4.5 Testing and Evaluation Processes

In this research, we aim to provide a rigorous evaluation of the quantized LLMs to determine their suitability for deployment in small business settings under resource constraints. Instead of training or fine-tuning these already pre-trained models, we will focus on testing and analyzing their performance based on existing parameters and configurations, ensuring a fair comparison between them.

The testing process consists of evaluating each model five (5) times on both the WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp platforms as well, providing an assessment of their performance capabilities. To ensure that the models are tested under realistic conditions, we will pass supply chain data, totalling 1069 words, to each model. This iterative approach will allow us to account for occasional anomalies or instabilities and capture the models' performance variance. This method allows us determine the optimal configurations for deploying LLMs in small business settings under resource constraints.

Below, are a more detailed outline of the test procedure:

1. Initialize the quantized LLM in both the WasmEdge and Python environments.
2. Present the same supply chain data, consisting of 1069 words, fed as a `.TXT` input file, to the LLMs on both platforms.
3. Repeat steps 1 and 2 four more times, ensuring each LLM is tested five times on both platforms.
4. In all cases, use `Perf` profiling / observation and NVIDIA's `nvidia-smi` tool to extract performance parameters such as total runtime or time elapsed, resource utilization (e.g.,

CPU, GPU, memory), task-clock, context-switching, CPU-migrations, page-faults, cycles, branch-misses, branches, and finally, instructions.

5. After inference is generated, the text is thoroughly subjected to inference quality assessment to check for metrics like completeness, coherence, error, tone of cautiousness, and other indicators.
6. After completing the tests, calculate the average performance metrics for each LLM on both platforms. This averaging will provide a statistical estimation of their performance.
7. To ensure that any observed differences in performance are genuine and not mere coincidence, ensure you repeat the process several times.

4 Application & Testing

The objective of this study is to evaluate the performance of five quantized language models (LLMs) in handling supply chain risk data within resource-constrained environments. To achieve this goal, we designed an experimental setup with specific hardware constraints and supply chain data to test and compare the performance of the LLMs.

4.1 Hardware and software.

In this section, we will describe the hardware and software configurations, the choice of quantized language models, and the supply chain risk data used in this study.

4.1.1 Hardware and Software Configurations

Our experimental setup involved a Linux Ubuntu 22.04 Jammy LTS laptop equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1065 GPU, featuring 6GB of VRAM, 32GB of system RAM, and only a 100GB free disk space. We opted for this setup due to its relatively modest hardware specifications, allowing us to mimic the resource-constrained environments often encountered in real-world scenarios.

We specifically chose an old NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1065 computer with its peculiar GPU due to its wide availability, gaming abilities and compatibility with various software packages and libraries. Its 6GB of VRAM offered a good balance between performance and affordability, making it an ideal candidate for our resource-constrained setup. The 32GB of system RAM facilitated efficient processing and minimized the likelihood of encountering memory-related issues during experimentation. These components were already installed in the gaming notebook which we used.

The brand name was 'Predator G3-571', of the 'Predator Helios 300' family, and came with a CPU specification: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700HQ clocking at a minimum speed of 2.80GHz. The CPU had 4 cores and 8 threads.

Below is a summary of the hardware specifications of the notebook we used for all the experiments:

Table 4.1: Computer notebook configuration for experimentation.

Components	Details
CPU / Processor:	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700HQ CPU @ 2.80GHz
Cores:	4
Threads:	8
Speed:	2.80GHz (Clock range: 3.40GHz)
Cache Sizes:	L1 Cache: 256 kB, L2 Cache: 1 MB, L3 Cache: 6 MB
Bridge Classes:	Xeon E3-1200 v6/7th Gen Core Processor Host Bridge/DRAM Registers
	6th-10th Gen Core Processor PCIe Controller (x16)
System Information	Details
Manufacturer	Acer
Product Name	Predator G3-571
Version	V1.10
Family	Predator Helios 300
Base Board Information	Details
Manufacturer	KBL
Product Name	Sienta_KLS
Version	V1.10
Chassis Information	
Manufacturer	Acer
Type	Notebook
Memory	
Total Installed Memory:	32 GB (16 GB SODIMM DDR4 in each slot)
Speed:	2667 MT/s
Form Factor:	SODIMM
Type:	DDR4
Manufacturer:	SK Hynix
Storage	
Disk 1:	256GB HFS256G39TND-N21
Disk 2:	1TB ST1000LM014-1EJ1
GPU	
	NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1065
GPU VRAM:	6GB
CUDA Version:	12.3
Display	1920 x 1080 pixels, Full HD

Network	WiFi: Realtek RTL8822BE 802.11ac PCIe Wireless Network Adapter
Bluetooth:	Bluetooth 4.2
Sound	High Definition Audio
Other	USB 3.0, HDMI, SD Card Reader, Webcam

Source: own results

The laptop's cooling system was functioning properly, keeping the temperature within safe limits during the experiments. The hard drive (SSD) read speed was measured at 289.07 MB/sec for /dev/sda.

4.1.2 Choice of Quantized Language Models

We selected five quantized language models (LLMs) to evaluate their performance in handling our supply chain risk sample data. The LLMs were chosen based on their low disk size and RAM requirements. Other factors we considered in their selection included their popularity, performance, and suitability for resource-constrained environments. These LLMs vary in terms of their architectural design, the number of parameters, and the techniques used training and quantization. The LLMs are:

1. Zephyr 7b-alpha
2. Llama-2-7b
3. Mixtral-8x7B
4. Microsoft's Phi-2 (with 2.7 billion parameters)
5. Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1

4.1.3 Supply Chain Risk Data

Our supply chain risk (SCR) sample data is needed for evaluating the performance of the LLMs in handling real-world SCR scenarios. For this study, we performed our tests with collected supply chain risk data primarily from a news article, (LaRocco, 2024) but also double-checked with industry reports and other policy documents. We filtered and pre-processed the data to remove irrelevant information and ensure consistency in the format.

Figure 4.1: Snippet of supply chain risk data used to evaluate the models

“Red Sea supply chain inflation may be peaking already, new trade data suggests. The sharp, sudden spike in supply chain inflation caused by the Red Sea crisis and ongoing attacks on shipping vessels by Houthi rebels may have peaked on key global trade routes, based on analysis of the latest data from Xeneta, a leading ocean and air freight benchmarking platform. It tells CNBC that rates on ocean routes from Asia to Europe and the Mediterranean are beginning to decline, but for U.S.-bound trade, prices are still climbing.....”

Source: CNBC news

The complete dataset comprised 1069 words of text related to supply chain news, covering topics such as supply chain disruptions, inflation, trade policies, share appreciations and geopolitical risks. The dataset was duplicated into five parts, with each LLM tested on each part separately. We used the same dataset to test the LLMs in both WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp environments.

4.2 Implementation Details

This section will attempt to outline the concrete details of how our models were deployed on WasmEdge and Python platforms.

4.2.1 WasmEdge Implementation

WasmEdge’s documentation states that it is an open-source web assembly runtime that is powered by the WebAssembly System Interface (WASI) and compatible with the WebAssembly standard. WasmEdge supports the component model proposal, allowing it to recognize the component and module format, thereby reducing its size and need for update with external dependencies. WasmEdge provides a ggml backend option that supports OpenBLAS, Metal, and cuBLAS.(WasmEdge, n.d.) Though WasmEdge is increasingly advantageous for rapid cold start times of AI applications, its nascent development presents limited options for deployment of AI tasks in Wasm binary formats. (Khelifa et al., 2024)

The ‘ggml’ backend of WasmEdge provides several metadata options, including enabling logging, printing the inferred tokens in streaming mode to standard output, setting the context size, setting the number of tokens to predict, setting the number of layers to store in VRAM, reversing the prompt, and setting the batch size for prompt processing. This flexibility helped us

in experimenting with optimal settings for our LLMs. The following command demonstrates how to use WasmEdge to load GGUF versions of the LLM models and run it with the specified options:

Listing 4.1: WasmEdge Function to load and LLM models

```
#!/bin/bash
# Define the fixed prompts
prompts=(
  "
  Analyse & summarize the news from a supply chain point of view (avoid
verbosity):
  * Major Entities involved,
  * Key policy designations in the news,
  * Company/Entity Profile,
  * Competitors,
  * Market valuation,
  * Impact on stocks,
  * Industries Impacted,
  * Tone,
  * Risk Rating 0 - 10,
  * Justification for Risk Rating
  "
)
# File containing the text to be analyzed
text_file="./1069_Data.txt"
# Read the text from the file
text_to_analyze=$(cat "$text_file")
echo "Starting data collection for GPU and RAM usage..."
# Start collecting GPU and RAM data
watch -n 1 "echo \$(date +%Y-%m-%d\ %H:%M:%S),\$(nvidia-smi --query-gpu=utilization.gpu,utilization.memory,memory.total,memory.free,memory.used,power.draw,temperature.gpu --format=csv,noheader,nounits | awk -F', ' '{printf \"%s%%, %s%%, %s MiB, %s MiB, %s MiB, %s W, %s C\", \$1, \$2, \$3, \$4, \$5, \$6, \$7}' | tr -d '\\\n'),\$(free -m | awk '/Mem:/ {printf \"%s GB, %s GB, %s GB, %s
```

```

GB,%s GB\", \ $2/1024, \ $3/1024, \ $4/1024, \ $6/1024, \ $7/1024}') >> gpu_stat.csv"
&
data_collection_pid=$!

# Loop through the prompts and analyze the text
for prompt in "${prompts[@]"; do
    echo "Prompt: $prompt"
    echo "Text to Analyze: $text_to_analyze"
    wasmedge --dir ../ --nn-preload default:GGML:AUTO:../llama-2-7b-chat-
q5_k_m.gguf \
    ../llama-simple.wasm \
    -g 10 \
    --batch-size 3024 \
    --n-predict 10000 \
    --ctx-size 8024 \
    --log-enable \
    --prompt "$prompt $text_to_analyze"

# Assuming you only want to process the first prompt and then exit
kill $data_collection_pid # Stop the data collection
echo "Data collection completed."
exit # Exit after processing the first prompt
done

```

In the above command, the `--dir` flag sets the directory search path, and the `--nn-preload` flag loads the shared library. The model file `llama-2-7b-chat-q5_k_m.gguf` is loaded along with the component and module format. Other flag options, such as `-g`, `--batch-size`, `--n-predict`, `--ctx-size`, and `--prompt` are used to control the behaviour of the model.

4.2.2 Python Implementation

Python is a high-level programming language known for its simplicity, readability, and ease of use. In this study, Python version 3.10.12 is used with the `llama.cpp` library (Ggerganov, n.d.) to instantiate the model from a local file.

The following code demonstrates how to instantiate the model and run inference using the `llama.cpp` library:

Listing 4.2: Python code using 'llama_cpp' for instantiating the LLM models

```
import sys
import os
import time
from llama_cpp import Llama

# Suppress verbose output by redirecting to os.devnull
original_stdout = sys.stdout
sys.stdout = open(os.devnull, 'w')

# Configuration
model_path = "/home/llama-2-7b-chat-q5_k_m.gguf" # Path to local model file

# Define a fixed prompt or context to guide the model's responses
fixed_prompt = """ \
* Analyse & summarize the news from a supply chain point of view (avoid \
verbosity):, \
* Major Entities involved, \
* Key policy designations in the news, \
* Company/Entity Profile, \
* Competitors, \
* Market valuation, \
* Impact on stocks, \
* Industries Impacted, \
* Tone, \
* Risk Rating 0 - 10, \
* Justification for Risk Rating
"""

# Instantiate model from the local file
llm = Llama(
    model_path=model_path,
    n_ctx=8024,
    n_batch=3024,
```

```

n_predict=10000,
n_threads=8,
n_gpu_layers=100,
prompt=fixed_prompt,
stream=True
)

# Restore stdout so we can print the result
sys.stdout = original_stdout

# Generation kwargs
generation_kwargs = {
    "max_tokens": 8000, # Adjust as needed
    "stop": ["</s>"],
    "echo": False, # Echo the prompt in the output
    "top_k": 1 # Greedy decoding
}

def run_inference(prompt) :
    # Combine the fixed prompt with the user input
    full_prompt = fixed_prompt + prompt
    # Run inference
    response = llm(full_prompt, **generation_kwargs) # response is a dictionary
    # Unpack the generated text from the LLM response dictionary and return it
    return response["choices"][0]["text"]

def print_like_typing(text, delay=0.05) :
    """Prints the text like it's being typed."""
    for char in text:
        sys.stdout.write(char)
        sys.stdout.flush()
        time.sleep(delay)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    # Read the input file
    input_file_path = "/path_to_our_prompt_file/1069_Prompt.txt" # Specify the
path to the input text file here
    with open(input_file_path, "r") as file:

```

```

input_text = file.read()

# Run inference and print the result
result = run_inference(input_text)
print(result)

```

In the above code, the Llama class is instantiated with several parameters, including the model path, context size, batch size, number of tokens to predict, number of threads, number of GPU layers, prompt, and streaming option. The `run_inference` function combines the fixed prompt with the user input, runs inference, and returns the generated text.

The table 4.2 below summarizes the application versions used in this study.

Table 4.2: Application Versions

Application	Version
WasmEdge	0.13.5
Python	3.10.12
llama.cpp	

This section provided an overview of the implementation details for the WasmEdge and Python implementations. The WasmEdge implementation leverages the WebAssembly standard and the `ggml` backend (WasmEdge, n.d.), while the Python implementation uses the `llama.cpp` library to instantiate the model and run inference. `llama.cpp` enables LLMs generate inference with just minimal setup on a wide variety of hardware. (Ggerganov, n.d.)

4.3 Model Testing

When evaluating the quantized language models (LLMs) for supply chain data analysis, we recognized the importance of testing the models under different scenarios. Prior to testing, we tried to train the models using supply chain risk data. However, we suspended this effort due to the prohibitive cost, and especially upon realizing that the outcomes from our trained model closely resembled those from pre-trained models available online. Our decision was strengthened by the understanding that supply chain information entails multiple variables, thus requiring pre-trained models capable of generalization for greater suitability.

To gauge the proficiency of the five (5) LLMs, we subjected them to a rigorous examination involving a 1069-word supply chain news article. Our assessments covered several evaluation criteria, as previously mentioned in Section 3, focusing on facets such as Inference quality and resource utilization. We intentionally constituted a mix of objective and subjective criteria to achieve a comprehensive assessment of the models' capabilities. To ensure consistency and mitigate bias, we formulated a scoring system based on a five-point Likert scale. This framework assigned ratings from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating significantly poor alignment with the prompt and 5 signifying exceptional congruence. We employed this scoring method to fairly rank the models' performances. For the evaluation of Inference quality, we considered the following criteria:

- **Relevance to prompt:** (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)
- **Coherence & Flow:** (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)
- **General Accuracy:** (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)
- **Erroneous responses on unknown prompts:** (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)
- **Fluency:** (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)
- **Insight:** (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)
- **Specificity:** (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)
- **Understandability:** (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)
- **Tone of cautiousness:** (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non-committal)
- **Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting:** (1=Inconsistent, 5=Consistent)

We performed these tests five (5) times for every LLM, experimenting with both WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp alternatives. This technique served a dual purpose—firstly, it exposed the models' adaptability in coping with alternative runtime situations, and secondly, it helped us establish their compatibility across different platforms. With this technique, we attempted to know the best performing LLMs in different supply chain scenarios. Following this, we compiled the outcomes from all five runs or unique runtime tests and calculated averages, as well as the average magnitude of deviations from the mean and the percentage of the average magnitude

of deviations from the mean. We then interpreted these averages as representative of the overall performance across all runtimes, offering insight into the models' capabilities and limitations.

Subsequently, we collated the resulting outputs and corresponding performance metrics from all five runs or unique runtime tests and calculated averages, as well as the average magnitude of deviations from the mean and the percentage of the average magnitude of deviations from the mean. As earlier defined in our chapter 2, we list below further performance metrics we collected for every runtime process:

- **Task Clock** (msec)
- **Context Switches**
- **CPU Migrations**
- **Page Faults** (millions)
- **Cycles** (trillions)
- **Instructions** (trillions)
- **Branches** (billions)
- **Branch Misses** (millions)
- **Time Elapsed** (seconds)
- **User Time** (seconds)
- **Sys Time** (seconds)
- **Prompt context size**
- **No. of tokens to predict**
- **Number of layers to run on the GPU**
- **Batch size for prompt processing**

The above performance metrics were extracted using Perf-tools, version 6.5.8, and leveraging the logged statistics from WasmEdge version 0.13.5. With bash script, we utilized the perf tools to initialize models and extract the needed metrics. The command below was used for this purpose when testing Python/LLaMA.cpp:

Listing 4.3: Perf-tool command for extracting performance metrics.

```
perf stat -o perf_stats.txt python ./run_inference.py> script_output.txt
2>&1 && echo -e "\a\a"
```

The perf-tools, also known as Performance Counters for Linux (PCL), Linux perf events (LPE), or `perf_events`, are normally referred to as ‘event-oriented observability tools’. They enable advanced performance analysis and troubleshooting by providing data about different aspects of system behaviour. These tools allow us to identify kernel CPU usage, cache misses, memory I/O stalls, memory allocations, network issues, and thread behaviour. `Perf_events`, located under `tools/perf` in the Linux kernel, combines various Linux tracing features to give a detailed performance analysis of the LLMs interactions with the kernel. (*Linux Perf Examples*, n.d.)

Figure 4.2: Linux perf_events Event Sources

Source: The Brendan Gregg blog post on perf_events: <https://github.com/brendangregg/perf-tools>

The diagram above depicts various event sources that contribute to Linux `perf_events`. The image represents a high-level view of how the different components work together to enable performance profiling with Linux `perf_events` which perf-tools grants you access to. These

sources include the operating system itself, system calls, hardware performance counters (PMCs), kernel tracepoints, and user-defined probes. The diagram also illustrates how these event sources are categorized and flow into the CPU to generate performance data. (Brendangregg, n.d.)

To specify the model's outputs, we utilized predefined prompts as seen below, integrating them into both the WasmEdge and Python environments.

Listing 4.4: Prompts as structured guide to assist our model's inference generation

```
prompts=(  
"  
    Analyse & summarize the news from a supply chain point of view (avoid  
    verbosity):  
    * Major Entities involved,  
    * Key policy designations in the news,  
    * Company/Entity Profile,  
    * Competitors,  
    * Market valuation,  
    * Impact on stocks,  
    * Industries Impacted,  
    * Tone,  
    * Risk Rating 0 - 10,  
    * Justification for Risk Rating  
    "  
)
```

These prompts above served as structured guidelines for the LLMs to follow when analyzing and summarizing news articles from a supply chain perspective. They included instructions such as identifying major entities involved, key policy designations, company profiles, competitors, market valuation, impact on stocks, industries affected, tone analysis, risk rating (ranging from 0 to 10), and justification for the assigned risk rating. By embedding these prompts into the WasmEdge and Python environments, we ensured that the models generated outputs in accordance with the specified criteria. By using these prompts, we constrained each model's output, in a way that its responses were specific to the subject or topic in the data given.

Finally, we then used the `nvidia-smi` command via our Linux terminal to extract more GPU and memory usage parameters while each LLM model was running. Below are the parameters:

- **Date and Time**
- **GPU Utilization (%)**
- **Memory Utilization (%)**
- **Total GPU Memory (MiB)**
- **Free GPU Memory (MiB)**
- **Used GPU Memory (%)**
- **Used GPU Memory (MiB)**
- **Power Draw (%)**
- **Power Draw (W)**
- **GPU Temperature (°C)**
- **Total RAM (GB)**
- **Used RAM (%)**
- **Used RAM (GB)**
- **Free RAM (GB)**
- **Cached RAM (GB)**

These parameters played a crucial role in monitoring and recording the resource consumption of each Language Model (LLM), providing essential insights into the performance and efficiency of the models. By executing this function simultaneously with all WasmEdge runtimes, we were able to gather real-time data on GPU utilization, memory usage, and other key metrics, enabling us to make informed decisions regarding optimization strategies and resource allocation. This comprehensive monitoring approach facilitated proactive management of system resources, ensuring optimal performance and stability across all the Language Models we evaluated.

To initiate the collection of GPU and RAM data, we utilized the following command:

Listing 4.5: Nvidia-smi command for extracting GPU and RAM data while LLMs are running

```
watch -n 1 "echo \$(date +%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S),\$(nvidia-smi --query-gpu=utilization.gpu,utilization.memory,memory.total,memory.free,memory.used,power.draw,temperature.gpu --format=csv,noheader,nounits | awk -F', ' '{printf \"%s%%, %s%%, %s MiB, %s MiB, %s MiB, %s W, %s°C\", \$1, \$2, \$3, \$4, \$5, \$6, \$7}' | tr -d '\\n'),\$(free -m | awk '/Mem:/ {printf \"%s GB, %s GB, %s GB, %s GB, %s GB\", \$2/1024, \$3/1024, \$4/1024, \$6/1024, \$7/1024}') >> gpu_stat.csv" & data_collection_pid=$!
```

In summary, our careful testing revealed the merits and drawbacks of each LLM, confirming our conviction of the necessity of exhaustive evaluation before implementing any of such LLM solutions within the supply chain use case.

4.5 Deployment Strategies

Deploying quantized Language Models (LLMs) in production environments presents unique challenges, especially considering resource limitations. Thus, selecting the appropriate deployment platform is important for achieving optimal performance and meeting operational needs.

In our investigations, we explored two deployment strategies: WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp. As previously mentioned, WasmEdge serves as a web assembly runtime with built-in support for LLMs, while Python is a high-level programming language widely embraced in the machine learning (ML) community. With WasmEdge, we compiled the LLMs into web assembly modules and dynamically loaded them during runtime. It works well with modern browsers, has few requirements, and is easy to quickly set up. We embedded the WasmEdge functions within a bash script to facilitate testing. This script incorporated predefined prompts and instructions for analyzing text from a supply chain perspective. It started by defining fixed prompts and reading text from a specified .TXT file, then it initiates data collection for GPU and RAM usage using the `watch` command alongside `nvidia-smi`, as show in Listing 4.5. Then, the script loops through each prompt, analyzing the text using WasmEdge with the specified parameters. Once the analysis is completed, it terminates the data collection and exits the

script. This streamlined approach allows for efficient testing and evaluation of the WasmEdge deployment strategy.

On the other hand, leveraging Python presents its own merits. By utilizing it, we could access a vast ecosystem of ML libraries and frameworks, facilitating rapid prototyping and iteration. Also, Python's user-friendly syntax and extensive documentation simplified the development and refinement process of our LLMs.

Both deployment strategies offer unique advantages based on specific use cases. While WasmEdge enhances portability and reduces dependencies, Python provides access to a rich set of ML resources, making the development lifecycle straightforward. It is important to note that the selection of a deployment strategy is dependent on the specific needs and priorities of the application.

4.6 Validation, Error Mitigation, and Model Considerations

This section highlights the focus on confirming the accuracy and reliability of the results, as well as acknowledging the potential impact of model choices and error reduction tactics. To establish the validity and reliability of the experimental results, we conducted sensitivity analyses and explored potential sources of bias and error, accounting for the impact of experimental parameters and assumptions made during the design phase. Through monitoring and mitigation, we sought to enhance the credibility and validity of our findings.

Error Minimization Strategy

To minimize errors and increase the reliability of our results, we performed five (5) independent runs for each model and averaged the outcome measurements. This approach allowed us to account for variability and potential fluctuations in the models' performance. In this way, we tried to guarantee confidence in our conclusions.

Python vs. WasmEdge Output Consistency

Interestingly, we discovered that the Python inferences consistently produced identical outputs regardless of the number of iterations, suggesting possible limitations imposed by the codebase. On the other hand, the WasmEdge counterparts displayed varying results for each trial, indicating potentially superior adaptability and responsiveness.

Limited Options in WasmEdge

Compared to Python, WasmEdge possessed fewer environmental options and flags, restricting our ability to manipulate and optimize the output. Despite these constraints, we successfully executed our experiments and gathered valuable data for subsequent analysis.

Model Selection Criteria

Our choices for the five quantized LLMs were influenced by their compact quantization sizes, dictated by the hardware limitations we encountered. Among these models, only Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1, Phi-2 and Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 qualified as instruction models, possibly granting them a competitive edge for certain problem types. Meanwhile, the remaining three models—Zephyr-7b-alpha, and Llama-2-7b—functioned as chat models. These varying capabilities must be taken into consideration as a potential influence on the results.

As stated in Section 2.4.1, the authors of the HuggingFaceH4/Zephyr-7B-alpha model claimed that the model was not trained to prioritize human preferences, and explicitly warned that this could lead to problematic outputs (as seen in chapter 5, where this model consistently failed to return inference in the Python experiments and returned poor results in WasmEdge) when prompted in certain ways. This was a similar problem encountered with the Phi-2 model.

Parameter Count Variations

The models featured varying parameter counts, introducing another dimension to our analysis. Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 had 46.70 billion parameters and 2-bit quantization, whereas Microsoft's Phi-2 had only 2.7 billion parameters and 5-bit quantization. The rest of the models, including Zephyr 7b-alpha, Llama-2-7b, and Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1, each had 7 billion parameters and the same 5-bit quantization levels.

Impact of Quantization Levels

As per the quantization variations just mentioned above, this introduced yet another variable to our experimental design. For instance, Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 required 18.14 gigabytes of RAM despite having a mere 15.64 gigabyte footprint, posing a constraint for our hardware setup. Also, Phi-2 benefited from a far more conservative allocation of merely 4.57 gigabytes.

Balancing these conflicting factors dictated the choice of the models for our investigation.

In summary, our validation and sensitivity analysis above has tried to address potential sources of bias and error stemming from experimental parameters and design assumptions. The distinct qualities of our chosen models—namely, their varying parameter counts, instruction capabilities, and quantization levels—must be taken into account when interpreting our findings. Accounting for these disparities reinforces confidence in the reliability of our experimental results.

5 Final Results

This section will present the culmination of our work, outlining the final results achieved and giving interpretations to them.

5.1 WasmEdge Outperforms Python Across Platform Runtimes

The results from the five (5) different LLM models tested, show that all the models performed better when deployed on the WasmEdge platforms as opposed to the Python/LLaMA.cpp platforms. The Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 model consistently returned inference that was 9 times faster on WasmEdge, while the Llama-2-7b-chat model was 2 times faster on WasmEdge, than on Python/LLaMA.cpp. Microsoft Phi-2 performed 7.9x faster on WasmEdge than on Python/LLaMa.cpp. WasmEdge is built with C++ and operates by invoking low-level functions which executes processes faster. A likely reason is that WasmEdge can easily utilize JIT (Just-In-Time) compilations and runtime optimizations (WasmEdge, n.d.) to achieve the speeds that make it outperform Python on LLM Inference generation tasks.

The table below shows the comparative results of runtime durations for WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp.

Table 5.1: Comparison of Platform Runtime Durations (WasmEdge vs Python)

LLM Models	WasmEdge (secs)	Python & LLaMA.cpp (secs)	Speed Difference (WasmEdge/Python)
Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	302	2734.76	~9x
Llama-2-7b-chat	183	368.46	~2x
Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	111	367.55	~3.3x
Microsoft Phi-2	69.16	547.92	~7.9x
Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha	114	NaN	NaN

Source: Own results

Of all the models experimented with, they always created swifter inferences on WasmEdge. However, in our experimental setup, the Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha model consistently failed to produce any output when run with Python/LLaMA.cpp, but consistently yielded results when we ran it with WasmEdge, with an inference speed of 114 seconds. It is possible that this particular model used had attributes that caused this, as all the models were already pre-trained and obtained directly from HuggingFace's website.

Figure 5.1: Comparison of Platform Runtime Durations for different models

Inference Time Elapsed per LLM

Source: Own results

While analyzing the average performance metrics across five (5) runtimes for the various language models on the WasmEdge platform, we observed correlations between the parameters and the efficiency of inference. For example, among the models tested, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 exhibited the highest time elapsed, taking approximately 301.59 seconds, while Microsoft Phi-2 produced the shortest runtime of 69.16 seconds.

Table 5.2: Results for LLMs runtime duration with WasmEdge API

Average Performance Metrics (of 5 runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha	Microsoft Phi-2
Time Elapsed (seconds)	301.59	183.49	111.04	113.57	69.16
User Time (seconds)	1,065.78	628.2	377.49	294.11	232.33
Sys Time (seconds)	15.76	9.99	11.36	11.91	3.45
roduced as Inference	750.8	508.2	287	224.4	487
Prompt context size	10,000	8024	524	8,024	524
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10000	600	10,000	600
Number of layers to run on the GPU	5	10	5	5	10
Batch size for prompt processing	624	3024	524	524	524

Source: Own results

The table above shows that the number of words produced as inference varied across models, with Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 returning the highest output at 750.8 words per runtime, and Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 producing the least at 287 words.

Subsequently, when running the models on the Python/LLaMA_cpp platform, disparate patterns in performance metrics become evident across the language models tested. The Table 5.3 below shows that Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 exhibited the longest time elapsed, clocking in at approximately 2734.76 seconds, while Llama-2-7b-chat demonstrated a relatively shorter runtime at 368.46 seconds, compared with Mixtral. Differences in user time and system time were also observed, with Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 showing the highest user and system times among the models tested. In terms of words produced as inference, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 again outperformed the other models, generating 4593 words, while Llama-2-7b-chat yielded the least at 234 words.

Both experiments in the two platforms (WasmEdge vs Python/LLaMA.cpp) required the use of different model settings, such as; prompt context size, number of tokens to predict, number of layers to run on the GPU, and batch size for prompt processing. We confirm that these differences posed resource constraints that significantly contributed to the observed variations in performance.

Table 5.3: Results for LLMs runtime duration with Python & LLaMA_CPP

Average Performance Metrics (of 5 runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Time Elapsed (seconds)	2734.76	368.46	367.55	547.92	NaN
User Time (seconds)	17480.87	1,821.23	1759.18	3377.71	NaN
Sys Time (seconds)	1151.39	114.17	118.18	237.88	NaN
Words produced as Inference	4593	234	295	1463	NaN
Prompt context size	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	NaN
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	NaN
Number of layers to run on the GPU	100	100	100	100	NaN
Batch size for prompt processing	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024	NaN

Source: Own results

Figure 5.2: Results for LLMs runtime duration with WasmEdge

Inference time (in seconds) for each models given 1047 words input only

Figure 5.3 Results for LLMs runtime duration with Python & LLaMA_CPP

Source: Own results

5.2 Higher Kernel Instructions Count Correlates with Longer Runtimes

When comparing the performance metrics for all models on WasmEdge versus Python/LLaMA.cpp, significant differences emerge, especially in terms of cycles, instructions, and branches executed.

On WasmEdge, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 demonstrated the highest number of cycles at 3.07 trillion, followed by Llama-2-7b-chat and Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1. Similarly, on Python/LLaMA.cpp, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 also exhibited the highest number of cycles, but at a significantly higher magnitude of 55.8 trillion. Below is a chart showing the variations of

instructions, cycles and branches when we ran each of the language models on the WasmEdge platform.

Figure 5.4 Results for performance profiles of LLMs on WasmEdge

Source: Own results

Figure 5.5 Results for performance profiles of LLMs on Python & LLaMA_CPP

Source: Own results

The figures above and the tables below confirm that for instructions executed, WasmEdge reported substantially lower numbers compared to Python/LLaMA_cpp across all models. This trend is consistent for branches executed as well, where WasmEdge shows lower figures than Python/LLaMA_cpp. Due to technical issues, Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha's performance metrics were not available for Python/LLaMA_cpp.

Table 5.4: Cycles, Instructions and branches on WasmEdge

Average Performance Metrics (of 5 runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Cycles (trillions)	3,071,654,565,766	1,811,856,101,829	1,103,554,381,806	672,560,135,705	869,619,204,008
Instructions (trillions)	6,292,145,098,093	2,972,996,568,347	2,130,139,027,571	1,149,226,807,571	1,669,740,288,046
Branches (billions)	573,249,253,227	238,352,273,377	155,503,520,463	109,404,842,373	143,363,383,740
Time Elapsed (seconds)	301.59	183.49	111.04	69.16	113.57

Source: Own results

Table 5.5: Cycles, Instructions and branches on Python/LLaMA_cpp

Average Performance Metrics (of 5 runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingface h4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Cycles (trillions)	55,845,802,377,596	5,391,388,815,705	5,228,805,477,088	10,064,157,554,790	NaN
Instructions (trillions)	67,819,509,520,363	8,833,859,223,799	8,975,176,905,801	10,885,953,278,273	NaN
Branches (billions)	7,719,756,913,924	381,839,717,060	353,751,259,101	1,010,990,638,487	NaN
Time Elapsed (seconds)	2734.76	368.46	367.55	547.92	NaN

Source: Own results

The Tables 5.4 and 5.5 above present a quick comparison of the performance profiles during runtime. In analyzing the performance metrics across WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA_cpp runtimes, it becomes apparent that some models exhibited higher kernel instruction counts, correlating with longer runtimes. The same trend is apparent in the task clock, context switching and CPU migration values for both platforms, with WasmEdge consistently outperforming Python/LLaMA_cpp on all indices. Amongst all the models, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 consistently generated the highest number of counts for all parameters as seen in the tables below.

Table 5.6: Task clock, context switches, CPU migrations on WasmEdge

Average Performance Metrics (of 5 runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Task Clock (msec)	1,105,851.99	652,621.71	397,250.22	243,050.66	313,147.95
Context Switches	31,677	22,744	9,215	10,265	18,139
CPU Migrations	4,686	3,067	1,159	1033.8	1,159
Page Faults (millions)	2,140,267	1,318,272	813,101	538,765	831,311
Branch Misses (millions)	921,931,155	444,667,385	219,561,295	204,146,032	196,786,322

Source: Own results

Figure 5.6 Chart of Task clock, context switches, CPU migrations on WasmEdge

Source: Own results

Table 5.7: Task clock, context switches, CPU migrations on Python/LLaMA.cpp

Average Performance Metrics (of 5 runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Task Clock (msec)	18,655,471.28	1,936,548.73	1,878,592.65	3,621,586.14	NaN
Context Switches	6,519,776	306,975	328,162	780,953	NaN
CPU Migrations	14,846	1,649	1,730	1,803	NaN
Page Faults (millions)	504,046	1,241,333	448,698	879,325	NaN
Branch Misses (millions)	10,692,341,408	1,139,196,665	1,137,115,274	2,381,853,410	NaN

Source: Own results

Figure 5.7: Task clock, context switches, CPU migrations on Python/LLaMA_cpp

Source: Own results

The performance metrics across WasmEdge and Python/LLaMa.CPP platforms reveal distinct correlations and consistencies. A notable trend was that on WasmEdge, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 demonstrated the highest task clock at 1,105,851.99 msec, while Llama-2-7b-chat showed the shortest at 652,621.71 msec. Context switches were highest for Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and lowest for Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1, suggesting varying degrees of multitasking efficiency. Similarly, on Python/LLaMa.CPP, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 exhibited the longest task clock at 18,655,471.28 msec, while Llama-2-7b-chat displayed the shortest at 1,936,548.73 msec. Consistent with WasmEdge, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 showed the highest context switches, indicating a potential correlation between task complexity and context switching frequency across both platforms.

5.3 Inference Quality Dominance

This section attempts to have a closer look at the quality of the inference generated by each model, then finds relationships between performance metrics of each model.

5.3.1 Prioritizing Inference Fidelity Over Computational Speed

Using a carefully prepared Likert scale, our inference results were analysed manually by a human eye, and the results confirmed that computational efficiency or short inference runtimes do not necessarily translate into superior inference quality. Quicker runtimes tended to come with significant trade-offs in inference quality. When our supply chain data was passed into the five language models using WasmEdge, we observed lower-quality inference and higher computational efficiencies from Microsoft Phi-2, Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha, and Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1. These three models had shorter runtimes or 'time elapsed' and fewer cycles, instruction counts and branches. Figures 5.4 and 5.5 in the sub-section 5.2 above on kernel instructions shows that Mixtral and LLaMA consistently executed the highest instructions, cycles and branches.

We observed also, that in both WasmEdge and Python, higher scores in inference quality metrics correlated with longer time elapsed, more cycles, more instructions issued, and more branches executed. In addition, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and Llama-2-7b-chat consistently scored higher for relevance to the prompt, coherence & flow, general accuracy, and fluency compared to Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1, Microsoft Phi-2, and Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha.

Table 5.8: Inference quality assessment for all models on WasmEdge

Inference Quality Assessment:	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	4.16	4.16	2.64	1.2	1.78
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	4.36	4.3	2.46	1.5	1.76
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	4.35	4.18	3.14	1.76	1.8
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts. (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	4.2	5	2.14	2.6
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	4.8	4.58	2.2	1.8	1.975
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	4.02	3.56	2.24	1.8	1.64
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	3.8	3.7	2.28	1.4	1.62
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	2.04	2.8

Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non-committal)	5	3.2	5	1	1.8
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	4.46	2.8	2.36	1.4	1.4
Time Elapsed (seconds)	301.59	183.49	111.04	69.16	113.57
Cycles (trillions)	3,071,654,565,766	1,811,856,101,829	1,103,554,381,806	672,560,135,705	869,619,204,008
Instructions (trillions)	6,292,145,098,093	2,972,996,568,347	2,130,139,027,571	1,149,226,807,571	1,669,740,288,046
Branches (billions)	573,249,253,227	238,352,273,377	155,503,520,463	109,404,842,373	143,363,383,740

Source: Own results

Figure 5.8: Visualized Inference quality assessment for all models on WasmEdge

Source: Own results

On the other hand, Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1, Microsoft Phi-2, and Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha showed lower performance across multiple quality metrics, indicating varying degrees of alignment with the given prompts and effectiveness in language generation.

As shown in the Table 5.10 and Figure 5.9 below, when the same experiments were performed with Python/LLaMA.cpp, it returned poor quality inference across all boards. Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and Llama-2-7b-chat that consistently scored more than 80% in WasmEdge, exhibited a significant degradation in inference quality when run in Python/LLaMA.cpp.

In fact, the language models evaluated in Python/LLaMA.cpp tended to consistently send 10 times more instructions than those in WasmEdge, with at least twice as long runtimes. Ironically, this resulted in much worse results, confirming an inefficient use of resources by Python. The table below shows that when the experiments were executed in Python, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 consistently returned the highest instruction count of 67 trillion, followed by Llama-2-7b-chat with 8,8 instructions. However, we observed that in this same Python setup, Llama-2-7b-chat always returned about 2 trillion less instructions than Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 and Microsoft Phi-2 sent over 10 trillion, being the second largest instructions count after Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1. This pattern differed from our observations in WasmEdge.

Table 5.9: Inference quality assessment for models on Python/LLaMA_cpp

Inference Quality Assessment:	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	3	2.8	3	1	NaN
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	2.9	2.9	2.9	1	NaN
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	3	3	1	NaN
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts. (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	5	5	1	NaN
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	2	2	3	1	NaN
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	2.3	2	2.6	1	NaN
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	2.1	2	2	1	NaN
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	1	NaN
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non-committal)	1	4	3	1	NaN
Completeness & Consistency of	3	3.8	4	1	NaN

Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)					
Time Elapsed (seconds)	2734.76	368.46	367.55	547.92	NaN
Cycles (trillions)	55,845,802,377,596	5,391,388,815,705	5,228,805,477,088	10,064,157,554,790	NaN
Instructions (trillions)	67,819,509,520,363	8,833,859,223,799	8,975,176,905,801	10,885,953,278,273	NaN
Branches (billions)	7,719,756,913,924	381,839,717,060	353,751,259,101	1,010,990,638,487	NaN

Source: Own results

Figure 5.9: Visualized Inference quality assessment for all models on Python/LLaMA_cpp

Source: Own results

Except for Python where half of our inference returned defective duplicates, the observations highlight in general, that Mistral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 with WasmEdge always returned the best inference quality, always showing a full grasp of context. Conversely, LLaMA in WasmEdge displayed superiority in handling larger context sizes and token predictions without crashing, unlike Zephyr, Mistral, and PHI-2, which required lower values to prevent crashes. This

difference points towards LLaMA's higher reliability and capacity for larger data inputs, which is crucial for generating detailed and coherent textual responses.

Our observations underscore the vital importance of tracking performance metrics in model evaluations because it shows consistently that the model's efficiency can be abstracted from it. From our observed results above, we can infer that models that exhibit higher counts of instructions and branches indicate a potentially more complex computational process and decision-making pathways in runtime. Higher counts of branches may also suggest more intricate decision trees and computational pathways. Higher cycle counts suggest a substantial amount of computational workload, which might impact a model's performance and efficiency. Always, these values should be interpreted in conjunction with the "instructions per cycle" values, which help to establish parameters for measuring efficiency, because lower instruction per cycle count generally indicates better efficiency in instruction execution per CPU cycle.

5.3.2 Model Inference Peculiarities & Use Case Suitability

Both Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and Llama-2-7b-chat models tended to generate more coherent, structured, and content-rich textual responses. This always indicates a superior model understanding and text generation capability, making it preferable for tasks requiring high-quality outputs. However, notable mention was the parameter we measured, called the "tone of cautiousness". We evaluated all five models using the Likert scale, using the band "1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non-committal".

Table 5.10: Likert scale scores for tone of cautiousness in WasmEdge

Inference Quality Assessment (average of 5 sample runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Tone of Cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non-committal)	5	3.2	5	1	1.8

Source: Own results

Table 5.9 above in Section 5.3.1 shows that Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 tended to show the highest degree of 'cautiousness'. In fact, they proved to be highly 'non-committal' in responding to questions involving the analysis of supply chain data that they had little information about. This pattern was observed with lesser intensity in Llama-2-7b-chat,

while the opposite was the case in Microsoft Phi-2 and Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha which were very 'certain and confident' in their evaluation of results. On closer inspection, Microsoft Phi-2 and Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha tended to score high in their falsely labelled certainty and confidence that did not translate into factual inference results.

For example, whenever Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 were asked to evaluate any given supply chain text data, where the information was unclear, they almost always returned a non-committal response as follows:

* **Market valuation:** *"No specific market valuation is mentioned."*

* **Impact on stocks:** *"No specific impact on stocks is mentioned."*

The opposite was the case in Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha, which answered most of the time with a false "certainty". While Mixtral-8x7b and Mistral-7b returned cautious responses for the same news item give, Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha gave completely fake results, while presenting them with "certainty and confidence". One of the false responses looked like this:

* **Market valuation:** *"According to the World Bank, global trade has declined by 2% in Q4 2018 due to a combination of factors including slowing economic growth in China, the trade war between the U.S. and China, and the ongoing Brexit saga. In 2019, however, global trade is projected to grow by 2.6%."*

* **Impact on stocks:** *"Shares in ocean carriers such as MSC, CMA CGM, Evergreen Line, ZIM Integrated Shipping Services, Hapag-Lloyd, Orient Overseas Container Line (OOCL) and Mediterranean Shipping Company (MSC) have seen mixed results."*

Table 5.11: Likert scale scores for erroneous responses in WasmEdge

Inference Quality Assessment (average of 5 sample runtimes)	Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Llama-2-7b-chat	Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Microsoft Phi-2	Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts. (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	4.2	5	2.14	2.6

Source: Own results

This pattern was consistent with other inference quality metrics such as "erroneous responses on unknown prompts". The same models in table 5.9 that produced false results with apparently "high certainty" also produced erroneous responses as shown in table 5.10.

With respect to use case suitability, models with a cautious and non-committal tone might be ideal for scenarios where certainty is uncertain, or where decisions carry a significant risk. Some use cases may include financial forecasting, legal document analysis, and medical diagnosis where errors or misinterpretations can have severe consequences. While models that tend to return results that might be prone to error might be more suitable in tasks related to generating rough outlines for content creation or generating brainstorming ideas, that do not require high precision and accuracy. Finally, with respect to models that score high on relevance of prompt, coherence & flow, general accuracy, specificity, etc., they could be considered more suitable for tasks that require precise and coherent language generation, such as academic research paper summarization, generating product descriptions for e-commerce platforms, or summarizing legal documents.

As stated in Section 2.4.1, we will like to remind the readers to interpret the results from HuggingFaceH4/Zephyr-7B-alpha with caution, since the authors of the model claimed that the model was not trained to prioritize human preferences, and explicitly warned that this could lead to problematic outputs when prompted in certain ways. (HuggingFaceH4/Zephyr-7b-alpha · Hugging Face, 2001)

5.4 Resource Utilization Patterns

We observed a consistent pattern in the resource utilization in 4 of 5 LLM models on the WasmEdge platform. We tracked the the resource utilization of the models with the `'nvidia-smi'` API that allowed us to log several metrics while the models were generating inference. For example, once the model is initialized, we observed a sudden spike in GPU utilization, Power Drawn, and GPU memory consumed. With each model Initialization, resource utilization in the first 60 seconds always saw an instant consumption of more than 70% in all runtimes. However, this peak suddenly drops for power drawn, and GPU utilization, while the GPU memory always remained at least 70% utilized through out the model's inference generation process.

Figure 5.10 below shows how GPU memory remained at roughly 95% throughout the entire runtime of the Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 LLM model's runtime. It also shows the power drawn throughout the entire 3 minutes inference period on WasmEdge. Notice how the RAM used remains quite unaffected through the entire inference time.

Figure 5.10: Resource utilization for Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 on WasmEdge

Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 resource consumption

Source: Own results

Since performance testing across each of the five (5) models revealed consistent resource utilization patterns in at least four of five runs of each model, we decided to summarize the log of each model by generating one representative chart for each model as we did above for figure 5.10 and subsequent charts below.

A notable observation in Figure 5.10 above, as compared with other Figures 5.11, 5.12, 5.13, and 5.13 below shows that Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 was the most computationally intensive model that made full use of the GPU memory. It was the only model amongst those under review that persistently consumed more than 95% of the GPU memory, while the Llama-2-7b-chat, Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 and Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha consumed an average of 65% of GPU memory through out the entire runtime of the model.

After the sudden spike, power drawn, remains around an average of 20% utilization in majority of the runtimes, confirming that the biggest consumption only occurs at model inference initialization, then it tapers and remains constant.

Figure 5.11: Resource utilization for Llama-2-7b-chat on WasmEdge

Source: Own results

Figure 5.12: Resource utilization for Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 on WasmEdge

Source: Own results

Figure 5.13: Resource utilization for Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha on WasmEdge

Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha resource consumption

Source: Own results

Figure 5.14: Resource utilization for Microsoft Phi-2 on WasmEdge

Microsoft Phi-2 resource consumption

Source: Own results

On the other hand, Microsoft Phi-2 was the only model that differed in its GPU memory consumption. We observed that it only consumed around 20% at all times. This points to a computational efficiency that did not correlate with inference quality.

Lastly, we confirm that inference generation on the WasmEdge platform in this experimental setup depended majorly on GPU memory (also known as VRAM), rather the RAM (system RAM) utilization. In all the models except Microsoft Phi-2, RAM consumption hardly went above 10% of the total 32 Gigabytes capacity of our computer. However, our 6 Gigabytes VRAM was always 95% utilized in 4 of 5 language models under review. Given these findings, our use case should prioritize investments in GPU resources over system RAM, ensuring sufficient allocation of VRAM, especially for the four language models displaying consistent high utilization. This may involve optimizing GPU memory management and potentially upgrading VRAM capacity to maintain optimal performance during inference generation on the WasmEdge platform.

6 Conclusion

This research has shed light on aspects related to the computational enhancements in supply chain risk analysis. We have carefully run comparative analysis of supply chain data on WasmEdge and Python, analysing them with five quantized large Large Language Models (LLMs), including Mixtral-8x7b-Instruct-v0.1, Llama-2-7b-chat, Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1, Huggingface4_Zephyr-7b-alpha and Microsoft Phi-2. Each model was tested five consecutive times on the same 1069-word supply chain data as shown in the Appendix section. This detailed investigations helped to establish suitable candidates for supply chain risk analysis, specifically in resource-constrained setups. A detailed literature review in Section 3 showed a paucity of documented research in the applications of AI in the field of supply chain risk management (SCRM). Very little in-terms of scientific investigations has been done with regards to the application of machine learning (ML) to this field of SCRM. The little scientific information available mostly covers the use of basic text analysis and legacy techniques such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), traditional Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic, basic ML model, RoBERTa and other BERT-based models.

Up until the publication of this thesis research, we are yet to encounter up to four solid publications that explore or propose the applied usage of Large Language Models (LLMs). There are barely one or two having anything to do with LLMs.

Our findings will help small enterprises doing SCRM to quickly set up such LLMs to assist their work. The research also enumerates required hardware and scenarios for optimal performance, energy savings and quick inference generation.

6.1 Summary of thesis research

The research findings present several major highlights:

*** Best platform for model deployment:**

The WasmEdge WebAssembly API outperforms python in runtime speed across all five (5) quantized LLM models were tested on them. The least comparative speed of the models tested on WasmEdge proved to be two times (2x) faster than Python/LLaMA_CPP deployments. In the best case, we had a model perform nine times (9x) faster in WasmEdge than in Python/LLaMA_CPP.

*** Longer inference time equals more text output :**

The five (5) quantized models with the longest inference times tended to produce longer text inferences as output. When Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 was given 1069 words of supply chain data to analyse on WasmEdge, it completed the task with the longest inference time of 301.59 seconds and produced 750.8 words . The second longest inference output for the same 1069 words of data, was Llama-2-7b-chat. This model completed the tasks in a shorter time of 183.49 seconds and inference output of 508.2 words comparative to that done by Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1. Other models like Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 and Huggingfaceh4_Zep-7b-alpha produced 111.04 seconds (with 287 words produced) and 113.57 seconds (with 224.4 words produced) respectively. Microsoft Phi-2, a 2.7 billion parameter model (the smallest of all by at least 2.5 times) returned the shortest inference time of 69.16 seconds, but strangely produced 487 words as inference output.

Conversely, the models when tested on Python/LLaMA_CPP platform always produced longer times and unstable results, with Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 producing over 4593 words (4300 of which were repetitive and duplicated gibberish) and an inference time of 2734.76 seconds compared to the 301.59 seconds in WasmEdge.

*** Shorter runtime does not necessarily translate into superior inference quality:**

When we used a Likert scale to score the inference quality of text produced by all 5 quantized models on both WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA_CPP, we observed that computational efficiency or short inference runtimes do not necessarily translate into superior inference quality. Quicker runtimes came with big trade-offs in inference quality. For example, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 with the longest inference completion time always produced the best inference quality, followed by Llama-2-7b-chat that always returned the second best inference quality for the second longest inference time. When this experiments were repeated in Python/LLaMA_CPP, it always returned a quality that was generally poorer across all boards and all models. Even Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 and Llama-2-7b-chat that consistently scored over 80% in WasmEdge, returned significantly degraded inference quality in Python/LLaMA_cpp.

Except for Python, where half of our inference returned defective duplicates, the observations highlight in general, that Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 with WasmEdge always returned the best inference quality, always showing a full grasp of context. Conversely, LLaMA in WasmEdge displayed superiority in handling larger context sizes and token predictions without crashing,

unlike Zephyr, Mistral, and PHI-2, which required lower values to prevent crashes. This difference points towards LLaMA's higher reliability and capacity for larger data inputs, which is crucial for generating detailed and coherent textual responses.

It is worth noting that models like Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1, even with a 2-bit quantization that had the biggest disk size and the highest RAM memory requirement on a resource-constrained setup tended to not crash in WasmEdge and always outperform all the models in inference quality, but not on resource utilization and runtimes. As Table 5.2 in chapter five (5) shows, despite limitations set to reduce memory usage (prompt context, 10,000 predicted tokens, 5 GPU layers, and a small batch size of 624), Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 (that required at least 18GB of our maximum 32GB RAM) achieved the best inference quality without encountering memory errors. This suggests these settings represent the maximum allowable configuration before the model crashes due to insufficient memory. On the other hand, Llama-2-7b-chat seemed to perform with a lower memory footprint compared to Mixtral, as it was able to run with a larger batch size of 3024 while having the same settings for prompt context (10,000) predicted tokens (10,000) and GPU layers (5). Conversely, Table 5.3 shows that Python had memory optimization strategy that prevented it from crashing on bigger values, pointing to memory reliability for all models (except Huggingfaceh4_Zephyr-7b-alpha which kept failing) through larger and consistent prompt context, predicted token settings and higher GPU Layers. This memory reliability in Python did not help significantly, as the inference output quality was always poorer than in WasmEdge.

*** Instructions, branches and cycles count correlates with longer runtimes of LLMs:**

Another significant outcome of this research was the discovery that both in WasmEdge and in Python, the models with the longest runtime that produced the best inference qualities correlated with having the highest number of cycles, instructions sent to kernel and branches created. For example, on WasmEdge, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 demonstrated the highest number of cycles at 3.07 trillion, followed by Llama-2-7b-chat and Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1. While in Python, Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 also exhibited the highest number of cycles, but at a significantly higher magnitude of 55.8 trillion. WasmEdge reported substantially lower numbers compared to Python/LLaMA_cpp across all models. This trend is consistent for branches executed as well, where WasmEdge shows lower figures than Python/LLaMA_cpp.

*** Model use case suitability:**

In Section 5.3.2, we observed a tendency by some models, but especially Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 to produce messages with a tone that was cautious and non-committal, especially when it was asked to return inference on a subject it had insufficient data on. This attribute is a feature that could make it suitable for scenarios where decisions that need to be made carry a significant risk, such as financial forecasting, legal document analysis and medical diagnosis.

*** Resource utilization patterns:**

Inference generation on WasmEdge (on our resource-constrained setup) consistently showed that GPU memory (also known as VRAM) was a better predictor of a model's inference speed, reliability, energy consumption, inference quality and stability than its RAM (system RAM).

Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 was the most computationally intensive model of all five, consuming persistently 95% of the GPU memory for at least 90% of the runtime. While the second largest was Llama-2-7B-Chat, Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 and Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha consistently consuming an average of 65% GPU memory for more than 90% of runtime.

All models exhibited a peculiar pattern of a sudden spike in GPU utilization, GPU memory used, and power drawn at the beginning of the runtime, possibly suggesting that the model draws more than 75% of the resources at initialization only, then it tapers out and remains at normal levels for the rest of the runtime, with GPU memory being the only exception to this pattern. During this spike, we notice that the model draws up to 80 or 90 Watts of power for a brief moment, then descends back to the baseline of about 25-35 Watts.

6.2 Contributions to the field

This research has made the following contributions to this field, namely:

- Propose a novel technique of using selected quantized lightweight LLMs for inference generation on resource-constrained setups with Supply Chain Risk Management data.

- Identify that quantized LLM models show a strong correlation between inference quality, inference duration and performance metrics such as Instructions executed, branches created and number of cycles produced.
- Identify that shorter inference times and best performance efficiency in quantized LLMs does not necessarily imply superior inference quality.
- Highlight the performance superiority of WasmEdge over Python for lightweight LLM inference generation

6.3 Future work

This study got the most favourable results on the WasmEdge. Python consumed a lot more time and returned poor quality inference. At the time of writing this publication, WasmEdge has indicated that work on WasmEdge for Python and Go are underway. It will be useful to redo such an experiment under such resource-constrained setups using WasmEdge in Python, Go and perhaps Rust. This will help to make more robust comparisons of the performance of these models in such setups.

Further research could involve profiling the model to analyze instruction breakdown, cycle counts, and branch behaviour. This sort of analysis would reveal the number of actual memory allocations and movements between addresses that occur during inference generation. This can help developers be more deliberate in the design, fine-tuning and modification of models performant models with an optimal resource utilization.

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<https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture10110504>

Appendix

1.0 Test system configuration:

Below is the computer used for the entire experimentation. The brand name was 'Predator G3-571', of the 'Predator Helios 300' family, and came with a CPU specification: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700HQ CPU at minimum speed of 2.80GHz. The CPU had 4 cores and 8 threads. The GPU specification: NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1065 GPU with 6GB of VRAM (or GPU memory). The physical RAM was 32GB.

Source: Own research

Source: Own research

2.0 Data Sample Used

The supply chain data below was a news item sourced from (LaRocco, 2024). It comprises 1069 words, 6308 characters (with spaces) and 5261 characters (without spaces). It was fed to all five quantized models for inference generation:

Red Sea supply chain inflation may be peaking already, new trade data suggests. The sharp, sudden spike in supply chain inflation caused by the Red Sea crisis and ongoing attacks on shipping vessels by Houthi rebels may have peaked on key global trade routes, based on analysis of the latest data from Xeneta, a leading ocean and air freight benchmarking platform. It tells CNBC that rates on ocean routes from Asia to Europe and the Mediterranean are beginning to decline, but for U.S.-bound trade, prices are still climbing. Average February short-term rates for forty-foot containers compared to the last round of general rate increases, implemented on January 16, show a slight decline. Forty-foot containers originating from the Far East to the Mediterranean per 40-foot container are set to be \$5,950 under February's GRIs. On January 16, rates were at the recent peak of \$6,050. On the trade route from the Far East to North Europe, rates for 40-foot containers are set to be \$4,820 at the start of February, slightly below the peak of \$4,850 on January 16. "Based on the fact the February general rate increases are below anticipated levels, this suggests ocean carriers have been forced to negotiate down with shippers," said Emily Stausbøll, Xeneta market analyst. She added this is the best indication of where the market is headed. "It now appears some shippers are pushing back and managing to agree to lower rates. So, we may see rates begin to flatten or decline sooner than many anticipated in February," she said. The overall rates are based on an average of all the transactions within each trade route — ocean shipping contracts are not uniformly set, and this is one of the reasons behind the slight decrease. Logistics CEOs tell CNBC they have the ability to negotiate prices down. Peter Sand, chief analyst for Xeneta, said as individual negotiations take place between shippers and ocean service providers, varied outcomes are to be expected. "Every shipper is impacted differently to the next," said Sand. "That's what creates so much uncertainty in the market because this is not a one size fits all situation." Some shippers have seen existing contracts honored during this crisis, while some have seen surcharges added. Some shippers have also had their contracts thrown out. "We see differences between how freight forwarders and ocean carriers treat their biggest customers because the power has never really been out of the hands of these extremely large volume shippers," he

said. Rates for cargo headed to the U.S. are still rising. But for U.S. companies, while some have negotiating leverage, shipping rates are not seeing any reprieve. According to Sand, rates for the trade route from the Far East to the U.S. East Coast are still heading higher. Amid the recent freight rate spikes which sent spot container prices as high as \$10,000, and resulted in some shippers moving more cargo to air freight, experts have worried about ocean carriers taking advantage of the crisis to excessively jack up prices. "Everyone is accusing everyone at the moment, which is normal during situations when there is so much uncertainty in the market," Sand said. "Ocean freight carriers did not invent this crisis and it takes time for them to put in new shipping networks to deal with the disruption caused by diverting away from the Suez Canal." However, Sand added, "You can also see this from the shippers' perspective who may view the rate increases as carriers acting opportunistically to maximize the money they can make." How Red Sea attacks impact global supply chain. Freight pricing pressure on additional trade routes may soon lessen. Maritime advisory firm Sea-Intelligence said the average delay for late vessel arrivals has "deteriorated," increasing by 0.30 days month over month to 5.35 days. But Stausbøll said following Lunar New Year, ocean carriers have the opportunity to realign vessel services which would take into account longer transit times around the Cape of Good Hope, which has impacted the delivery of trade. "There are plenty of ships to manage this increased sailing time, so we would expect other major trades to follow the same pattern as Far East into Europe and see rates flatten or reduce, albeit with a slight delay," Stausbøll said. She also tells CNBC there should be enough capacity in U.S. ports to handle the Red Sea diversions because demand is so much lower now than in 2021, and there are no longer any Covid-19 restrictions impacting workers in these ports. Still, other supply chain friction points are surfacing. In a Tuesday hearing on the impact of the Red Sea Crisis held on Capitol Hill, Jon Gold, vice president of supply chain and customs policy at the National Retail Federation, said the NRF was hearing from members that rail-bound container dwell times were starting to tick up. "Rail car imbalances and increased demand could result in more congestion and increases in dwell," Gold said. "We need to make sure there is chassis availability as well. One of the biggest drivers of congestion during the pandemic was the lack of available chassis." The NRF was also hearing from members of terminal appointment challenges for trucks to pick up containers. "Some believe this congestion could begin within the next four to six weeks, after Lunar New Year, when trade volumes start to pick up again," Gold warned. Paul Brashier, vice president of drayage & intermodal at ITS Logistics, said he is concerned about the ripple effects the Red Sea diversions will

have on West Coast ports after Lunar New Year, when many shippers are looking to shift back to the West Coast to avoid the lengthy Cape of Good Hope transit. "At the end of the day, the consumer will suffer the most as significant increases in ocean container rates are passed onto the consumer," he said. Resilinc, a supply chain mapping, disruption sensing, and analytics company, said the impact of the Red Sea crisis runs deep from a supply chain perspective. "Organizations with deeper pockets are going to weather this disruption with better outcomes," said Bindiya Vakil, CEO and co-founder of Resilinc. "The effects of canceled or delayed orders and increased costs are going to be felt by smaller companies and suppliers in the lower tiers of the supply chain.

3.0 Sources and links to APIs deployed

Glances: Open-source system cross-platform monitoring tool.

Citation: Nicolargo. (n.d.). GitHub - nicolargo/glances: Glances an Eye on your system. A top/htop alternative for GNU/Linux, BSD, Mac OS and Windows operating systems. GitHub.

URL: <https://github.com/nicolargo/glances>

Perf Tools: A performance analysis toolset for Linux ftrace and perf_events.

Citation: Brendangregg. (n.d.). GitHub - brendangregg/perf-tools: Performance analysis tools based on Linux perf_events (aka perf) and ftrace.

URL: <https://github.com/brendangregg/perf-tools>

WasmEdge: A lightweight, high-performance WebAssembly API for running lightweight LLMs.

Citation: WasmEdge. (n.d.). GitHub - WasmEdge/WasmEdge: WasmEdge is a lightweight, high-performance, and extensible WebAssembly runtime for cloud native, edge, and decentralized applications. It powers serverless apps, embedded functions, microservices, smart contracts, and IoT devices.

URL: GitHub. <https://github.com/WasmEdge/WasmEdge>

LLAMA.CPP: Enables LLMs generate inference with very little setup on a variety of resource constrained hardware, both locally and on cloud. It comes with plain C/C++ implementations without any dependencies, built with accomodation for 1.5-bit, 2-bit, 3-bit, 4-bit, 5-bit, 6-bit, and 8-bit integer quantization for faster inference and reduced memory use. (Ggerganov, n.d.)

URL: GitHub. <https://github.com/ggerganov/llama.cpp>

4.0 Repository links to download all quantized models used

i.) **Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1**

Model name: Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1

Model file format: GGUF

Model repository name-tag: TheBloke/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1-GGUF

Model creator: TheBloke/Tom Jobbins

Download URL: https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1-GGUF/main/mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1.Q2_K.gguf

Name	Quant method	Bits	Size	Max RAM required	Use case
<code>mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1.Q2_K.gguf</code>	Q2_K	2	15.64 GB	18.14 GB	smallest, significant quality loss - not recommended for most purposes

ii.) **Llama-2-7B-Chat**

Model name: Llama-2-7B-Chat

Model file format: GGUF

Model repository name-tag: TheBloke/Llama-2-7B-Chat-GGUF

Model creator: TheBloke/Tom Jobbins

Download URL: https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/Llama-2-7b-Chat-GGUF/main/llama-2-7b-chat.Q5_K_M.gguf

Name	Quant method	Bits	Size	Max RAM required	Use case
<code>llama-2-7b-chat.Q5_K_M.gguf</code>	Q5_K_M	5	4.78 GB	7.28 GB	large, very low quality loss - recommended

iii.) Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1

Model name: Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1-GGUF

Model file format: GGUF

Model repository name-tag: TheBloke/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1-GGUF

Model creator: TheBloke/Tom Jobbins

Download URL: https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1-GGUF/main/mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1.Q5_K_M.gguf

Name	Quant method	Bits	Size	Max RAM required	Use case
mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1.Q5_K_M.gguf	Q5_K_M	5	5.13 GB	7.63 GB	large, very low quality loss - recommended

iv.) Huggingfaceh4_Zephyr-7b-alpha

Model name: Huggingfaceh4_Zephyr-7b-alpha

Model file format: GGUF

Model repository name-tag: NA

Model creator: 'Hugging Face H4' - (<https://huggingface.co/HuggingFaceH4>)

Download URL: NA

Name	Quant method	Bits	Size	Max RAM required	Use case
	Q5_K_M	5	5.1GB		

iv.) Microsoft Phi-2

Model name: phi-2-GGUF

Model file format: GGUF

Model repository name-tag: TheBloke/phi-2-GGUF

Model creator: TheBloke/Tom Jobbins

Download URL: https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/phi-2-GGUF/main/phi-2.Q5_K_M.gguf

Name	Quant method	Bits	Size	Max RAM required	Use case
phi-2.Q5_K_M.gguf	Q5_K_M	5	2.07 GB	4.57 GB	large, very low quality loss - recommend

5.0 Complete table of experimental results on all quantized LLM models

In the following pages, we have included the full table for experimental results on all quantized LLM models performed both in the WasmEdge and Python/LLaMA.cpp platforms. It also contains columns for the 'average of 5 runs' which was the final consolidated value we used for each model. We have also included the 'average magnitude of deviations from the mean'. This represents the numerical deviation from the column titled 'average of 5 runs'. And finally we have a column named '% average magnitude of deviations from the mean'. For ease of readability, this was added to simply represent as percentage values the average magnitude of deviations from the mean of 5 runs. We included all these tables in this appendix section due to the thesis page count restrictions.

5.2 PYTHON Results for LLaMA-2-7B-Chat on Python/LLaMA.cpp Platform (Multiple Runs)

Llama-2-7B-Chat	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)		Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	% Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	1,844,229.93	1,871,319.46	2,057,970.69	1,972,674.84	1,868,913.11		1,936,548.73	78,774.04	3.8%
Context Switches	214,596	239,660	427,082	346,560	222,466		306,975	79,846.50	26.7%
CPU Migrations	1,314	1,375	2,090	1,815	1,184		1,649	304.00	20.4%
Page Faults (millions)	1,241,157	1,241,227	1,241,713	1,241,233	1,241,217		1,241,333	190.25	0%
Cycles (trillions)	5,135,856,650,344	5,210,191,509,693	5,728,665,421,749	5,490,841,681,032	5,204,342,269,325		5,391,388,815,705	218,364,735,686.00	3.8%
Instructions (trillions)	8,627,784,338,037	8,686,076,745,221	9,169,078,497,508	8,852,497,314,431	8,634,643,169,655		8,833,859,223,799	176,928,682,170.25	2%
Branches (billions)	333,912,804,000	348,271,293,938	459,685,068,632	385,489,701,670	334,586,410,591		381,839,717,060	40,747,668,091.00	10.8%
Branch Misses (millions)	1,031,302,473	1,061,563,954	1,302,455,267	1,161,464,967	1,026,238,777		1,139,196,665	92,763,451.75	8.3%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	364.62	353.23	386.01	369.99	351.87		368.46	9.54	2.8%
User Time (seconds)	1,754.61	1773.57	1905.69	1851.03	1774.48		1,821.23	57.14	2.9%
Sys Time (seconds)	88.74	96.67	150.99	120.27	93.44		114.17	21.46	18.6%
Prompt context size	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024		8,024	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000		10,000	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	100	100	100	100	100		100	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024		3,024	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047		1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	234	234	234	234	234		234	0	0%
Characters produced (Including spaces)	1588	1588	1588	1588	1588		1588	0	0%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	1312	1312	1312	1312	1312		1312	0	0%
Inference Quality Assessment:							Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	2.8	2.8	2.8	2.8	2.8		2.8	0	0%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9		2.9	0	0%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	3	3	3	3		3	0	0%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts. (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	2	2	2	2	2		2	0	0%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	2	2	2	2	2		2	0	0%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	2	2	2	2	2		2	0	0%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	4	4	4	4	4		4	0	0%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	3.8	3.8	3.8	3.8	3.8		3.8	0	0%

5.3 PYTHON Results for Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 on Python/LLaMA.cpp Platform (Multiple Runs)

Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)	Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	% Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	1,887,178.31	1,876,442.01	1,889,091.82	1,861,658.47	1,871,420.16	1,878,592.65	9,542.41	0.5%
Context Switches	339,770	330,481	334,956	307,441	313,758	328,162	10,360.50	3.6%
CPU Migrations	2,153	1,656	1,577	1,534	1,699	1,730	211.50	10%
Page Faults (millions)	449,030	448,547	448,587	448,627	448,716	448,698	166.13	0%
Cycles (trillions)	5,252,375,977,602	5,222,719,184,424	5,258,252,400,896	5,181,874,345,429	5,209,444,212,637	5,228,805,477,088	26,508,712,161.25	0.5%
Instructions (trillions)	8,988,441,268,213	8,978,592,081,398	8,999,615,889,678	8,934,058,383,914	8,962,307,482,400	8,975,176,905,801	20,559,260,943.38	0.2%
Branches (billions)	356,103,613,856	354,781,670,169	359,537,399,183	344,582,353,197	351,059,857,704	353,751,259,101	4,584,452,952.13	1.2%
Branch Misses (millions)	1,177,863,079	1,110,818,310	1,133,369,795	1,126,409,912	1,108,161,391	1,137,115,274	20,373,902.50	1.7%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	401.478324	356.4861576	358.11	354.11	355.91	367.5453432	16.97	4%
User Time (seconds)	1763.416878	1758.08	1766.45	1748.76	1757.84	1759.17524	5.76	0.3%
Sys Time (seconds)	122.644322	117.10	121.35	111.60	112.33	118.1754803	3.82	3.4%
Prompt context size	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	100	100	100	100	100	100	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	295	295	295	295	295	295	0	0%
Characters produced (including spaces)	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	0	0%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	0	0%
Inference Quality Assessment:						Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	0%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	0	0%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	0%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts: (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	5	5	5	5	5	0	0%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	0%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	0	0%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	5	5	5	0	0%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	0%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	4	4	4	4	4	4	0	0%

5.4 PYTHON Results for Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha on Python/LLaMA.cpp Platform (Multiple Runs)

As earlier stated in chapters 5 and 2, the Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha refused to produce any results when tested in Python/LLama.cpp

5.5 WasmEdge Results for Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1 on WasmEdge Platform (Multiple Runs)

Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)		Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	% Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	859,675.62	1,144,473.56	1,240,958.39	1,517,742.29	766,410.10		1,105,851.99	234,247.31	21.2%
Context Switches	22,142	45,470	30,193	38,082	22,500		31,677	8,079	25.5%
CPU Migrations	3,390	5,731	4,963	6,032	3,315		4,686	1,067	22.8%
Page Faults (millions)	1,687,902	2,204,023	2,393,715	2,902,331	1,513,364		2,140,267	431,707	20.2%
Cycles (trillions)	2,387,657,653,093	3,179,187,590,949	3,446,857,781,437	4,215,331,911,920	2,129,237,891,433		3,071,654,565,766	650,565,434,802.72	21.2%
Instructions (trillions)	5,002,579,667,946	6,367,107,984,304	7,104,029,597,995	8,603,274,489,697	4,383,733,750,522		6,292,145,098,093	1,279,190,711,087.04	20.3%
Branches (billions)	484,878,120,003	599,200,760,633	619,093,528,142	717,772,896,175	445,300,961,183		573,249,253,227	86,527,770,107.36	15.1%
Branch Misses (millions)	683,517,275	972,879,413	1,049,025,957	1,279,570,168	624,662,961		921,931,155	214,272,829.44	23.2%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	236.92	311.14	337.38	410.58	211.93		301.59	62	20.5%
User Time (seconds)	825.94	1,104.03	1197.01	1466.66	735.24		1,065.78	228	21.4%
Sys Time (seconds)	14.95	15.92	16.18	17.10	14.63		15.76	1	4.9%
Prompt context size	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000		10,000	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000		10,000	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	624	624	624	624	624		624	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047		1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	552	783	831	1061	527		750.8	169.04	22.5%
Characters produced (Including spaces)	3738	4840	5478	6871	3181		4821.6	1089.68	22.6%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	3126	4070	4514	5806	2674		4038	910.4	22.5%
Inference Quality Assessment:							Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	3	4	5	4.8	4		4.16	0.592	14.2%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	3.8	5	5	4	4		4.36	0.512	11.7%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	4.5	4.85	4.6	4.8		4.35	0.54	12.4%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts. (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	5	5	5	5	4		4.8	0.32	6.7%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	2.5	4	5	4.7	3.89		4.02	0.6656	16.6%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	3	4	5	4	3		3.8	0.64	16.8%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	4	5	5	4.5	3.8		4.46	0.448	10%

5.6 WasmEdge Results for LLaMA-2-7B-Chat on WasmEdge Platform (Multiple Runs)

Llama-2-7B-Chat	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)		Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	677,628.65	639,289.52	831,550.34	578,702.08	535,937.98		652,621.71	81,574.22	12.5%
Context Switches	29,795	28,199	23,214	17,909	14,603		22,744	5,190.40	22.8%
CPU Migrations	3,509	3,507	3,500	2,582	2,238		3,067	525.76	17.1%
Page Faults (millions)	1,366,417	1,286,295	1,664,436	1,177,171	1,097,039		1,318,272	157,723.92	12%
Cycles (trillions)	1,881,158,470,903	1,774,683,203,038	2,308,468,232,128	1,606,677,864,357	1,488,292,738,720		1,811,856,101,829	226,365,799,749.04	12.5%
Instructions (trillions)	3,062,862,345,398	2,848,711,699,498	3,791,943,346,411	2,671,685,034,133	2,489,780,416,293		2,972,996,568,347	363,525,022,046.32	12.2%
Branches (billions)	249,464,010,943	238,884,672,599	282,172,571,789	220,791,244,859	200,448,866,697		238,352,273,377	22,185,774,079.52	9.3%
Branch Misses (millions)	476,051,404	434,074,238	579,063,735	394,029,955	340,117,593		444,667,385	66,312,147.60	14.9%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	190.22	179.16	233.09	163.26	151.74		183.49	22.53	12.3%
User Time (seconds)	652.79	615.27	801.65	556.32	514.95		628.20	79.22	12.6%
Sys Time (seconds)	10.01	9.96	11.25	9.50	9.24		9.99	0.51	5.1%
Prompt context size	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024		8024	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000		10000	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	10	10	10	10	10		10	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024	3,024		3024	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047		1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	519	422	674	467	459		508.2	70.64	13.9%
Characters produced (Including spaces)	3295	2765	4455	2932	2874		3264.2	488.64	15%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	2793	2305	3793	2457	2425		2754.6	430.72	15.6%
Inference Quality Assessment:							Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	5	4	5	4	2.8		4.16	0.672	16.2%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	5	3.8	5	3.9	3.8		4.3	0.56	13%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	5	5	4	3.9		4.18	0.656	15.7%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts: (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	1	5	5	5	5		4.2	1.28	30.5%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	5	5	5	4	3.9		4.58	0.504	11%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	3.5	4	5	3	2.3		3.56	0.752	21.1%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	5	3.7	5	2.5	2.3		3.7	1.04	28.1%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	1	5	2	5	3		3.2	1.44	45%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	5	3	4	1	1		2.8	1.44	51.4%

5.7 WasmEdge Results for Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1 on WasmEdge Platform (Multiple Runs)

Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)		Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	427,049.73	259,152.35	416,407.87	460,719.32	422,921.82		397,250.22	55,239.15	13.9%
Context Switches	9,863	6,138	9,592	10,545	9,936		9,215	1,230.72	13.4%
CPU Migrations	1,287	777	1,227	1,285	1,217		1,159	152.64	13.2%
Page Faults (millions)	868,513	559,322	850,025	930,186	857,459		813,101	101,511.60	12.5%
Cycles (trillions)	1,186,402,168,366	719,881,096,101	1,156,585,705,168	1,279,602,986,995	1,175,299,952,401		1,103,554,381,806	153,469,314,282.08	13.9%
Instructions (trillions)	2,278,685,875,897	1,432,786,594,800	2,229,804,160,087	2,453,836,206,884	2,255,582,300,188		2,130,139,027,571	278,940,973,108.48	13.1%
Branches (billions)	162,672,178,151	126,934,029,386	159,134,021,861	168,020,178,115	160,757,194,802		155,503,520,463	11,427,796,430.80	7.3%
Branch Misses (millions)	230,844,036	144,402,763	241,563,360	241,491,750	239,504,566		219,561,295	30,063,412.80	13.7%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	118.85	74.76	116.15	127.70	117.72		111.04	14.51	13.1%
User Time (seconds)	406.75	243.43	395.80	439.08	402.36		377.49	53.62	14.2%
Sys Time (seconds)	11.39	10.29	11.78	11.78	11.63		11.36	0.43	3.8%
Prompt context size	524	524	524	524	524		524	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	600	600	600	600	600		600	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	524	524	524	524	524		524	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047		1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	315	153	351	324	292		287	53.6	18.7%
Characters produced (including spaces)	2097	1082	2234	2183	2065		1932.2	340.08	17.6%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	1736	879	1883	1818	1774		1618	295.6	18.3%
							Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Inference Quality Assessment:									
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	2.5	2	2.4	2.5	3.8		2.64	0.464	17.6%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	2.5	1.98	2.3	2.5	3		2.46	0.2528	10.3%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	3	2.9	3	3.8		3.14	0.264	8.4%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts: (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	2	2	2	2	3		2.2	0.32	14.5%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	2.2	1.9	1.9	2.2	3		2.24	0.304	13.6%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	2.2	2	2	2.2	3		2.28	0.288	12.6%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	2.2	2	2.4	2.2	3		2.36	0.272	11.5%

5.8 WasmEdge Results for Huggingface4_zephyr-7b-alpha on WasmEdge Platform (Multiple Runs)

Huggingface4_zephyr-7b-alpha	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)		Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	522,470.94	119,080.05	413,956.88	220,323.43	289,908.46		313,147.95	124,052.77	39.6%
Context Switches	34,162	25,991	9,748	8,376	12,419		18,139	9,549.84	52.6%
CPU Migrations	1,851	742	1,254	809	1,139		1,159	314.80	27.2%
Page Faults (millions)	1,468,242	741,288	843,110	486,527	617,388		831,311	259,492.00	31.2%
Cycles (trillions)	1,450,333,298,158	330,146,471,283	1,149,927,588,301	612,036,854,571	805,651,807,727		869,619,204,008	344,408,991,377.20	39.6%
Instructions (trillions)	2,715,666,726,828	707,227,274,602	2,181,433,504,187	1,201,941,365,407	1,542,432,569,208		1,669,740,288,046	623,047,861,968.88	37.3%
Branches (billions)	182,622,467,058	102,238,811,290	162,128,255,782	126,306,944,822	143,520,439,746		143,363,383,740	23,272,404,546.88	16.2%
Branch Misses (millions)	317,340,236	125,968,741	241,265,899	127,350,215	172,006,517		196,786,322	66,013,396.72	33.5%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	204.56	100.44	115.35	64.69	82.83		113.57	37.11	32.7%
User Time (seconds)	494.96	103.18	393.66	205.51	273.23		294.11	120.16	40.9%
Sys Time (seconds)	14.87	12.02	11.53	10.44	10.70		11.91	1.22	10.3%
Prompt context size	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024	8,024		8,024	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000		10,000	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	5	5	5	5	5		5	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	524	524	524	524	524		524	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047		1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	406	58	283	155	220		224.4	96.08	42.8%
Characters produced (Including spaces)	2540	345	1811	957	1303		1391.2	627.44	45.1%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	2147	288	1531	804	1085		1171	534.4	45.6%
Inference Quality Assessment:							Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	3.9	1	2	1	1		1.78	0.936	52.6%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	3	1	2	1.8	1		1.76	0.608	34.5%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	4	1	1	2	1		1.8	0.96	53.3%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts: (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	5	1	1	5	1		2.6	1.92	73.8%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	3.4	1	1.5		2		1.975	0.725	36.7%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	3	1	1.2	2	1		1.64	0.688	42%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	2.7	1	2	1.4	1		1.62	0.584	36%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	5	1	4	2	2		2.8	1.36	48.6%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	5	1	1	1	1		1.8	1.28	71.1%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	3	1	1	1	1		1.4	0.64	45.7%

5.9 WasmEdge Results for Microsoft Phi-2 on WasmEdge Platform

Phi2	Sample run (1)	Sample run (2)	Sample run (3)	Sample run (4)	Sample run (5)		Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Task Clock (msec)	243,100.22	242,551.79	234,837.02	247,788.08	246,976.19		243,050.66	3,485.00	1.4%
Context Switches	9,024	9,408	7,523	13,260	12,110		10,265	1,936.00	18.9%
CPU Migrations	993	1,008	762	1,227	1,179		1033.8	135.36	13.1%
Page Faults (millions)	538,793	538,771	524,183	546,050	546,030		538,765	5,832.96	1.1%
Cycles (trillions)	672,372,645,517	671,594,287,975	649,872,639,470	685,371,785,254	683,589,320,310		672,560,135,705	9,536,333,661.44	1.4%
Instructions (trillions)	1,153,496,982,069	1,139,542,952,156	1,122,421,568,940	1,168,667,884,854	1,162,004,649,835		1,149,226,807,571	14,595,637,618.24	1.3%
Branches (billions)	110,235,801,361	107,084,591,256	102,913,306,870	113,997,943,453	112,792,568,924		109,404,842,373	3,524,714,647.84	3.2%
Branch Misses (millions)	202,723,196	209,379,605	196,461,526	206,018,325	206,147,506		204,146,032	3,642,936.48	1.8%
Time Elapsed (seconds)	69.14	69.05	67.07	70.39	70.17		69.16	0.89	1.3%
User Time (seconds)	232.52	231.84	224.33	236.96	236.02		232.33	3.40	1.5%
Sys Time (seconds)	3.41	3.50	3.46	3.45	3.44		3.45	0.02	0.7%
Prompt context size	524	524	524	524	524		524	0	0%
No. of tokens to predict	600	600	600	600	600		600	0	0%
Number of layers to run on the GPU	10	10	10	10	10		10	0	0%
Batch size for prompt processing	524	524	524	524	524		524	0	0%
Words submitted for Inference	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047		1047	0	0%
Words produced as Inference	488	484	453	497	513		487	14.8	3%
Characters produced (Including spaces)	2807	3066	2789	2890	2996		2909.6	97.12	3.3%
Characters produced (excluding spaces)	2333	2600	2352	2402	2492		2435.8	88.16	3.6%
Inference Quality Assessment:							Average of 5 runs	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean	Average Magnitude of Deviations from Mean
Relevance to prompt: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	1	2	1	1	1		1.2	0.32	26.7%
Coherence & Flow: (1=Very poor, 5=Excellent)	1.5	3	1	1	1		1.5	0.6	40%
General Accuracy: (1=Inaccurate, 5=Highly accurate)	3	2.5	1.3	1	1		1.76	0.792	45%
Erroneous responses on unknown prompts: (1=Extremely erroneous, 5=Not erroneous)	4	2.5	2.2	1	1		2.14	0.912	42.6%
Fluency: (1=Disfluent, 5=Highly fluent)	3	3	1	1	1		1.8	0.96	53.3%
Insight: (1=No insight, 5=Deep insight)	3	3	1	1	1		1.8	0.96	53.3%
Specificity: (1=Not specific, 5=Highly specific)	2	2	1	1	1		1.4	0.48	34.3%
Understandability: (1=Hard to understand, 5=Very easy to understand)	3	4	1.2	1	1		2.04	1.168	57.3%
Tone of cautiousness: (1=Certainty & confidence, 5=Cautious & non committal)	1	1	1	1	1		1	0	0%
Completeness & Consistency of Response Formatting: (1=Inconsistent & 5=Consistent)	2	2	1	1	1		1.4	0.48	34.3%

6.0 Comparative performance profile patterns between WasmEdge and Python in 5 consecutive runs

We include charts of the comparative performance profile patterns. We highlight the variations in the **WasmEdge (left column)** runs versus those of **Python/LLaMA.cpp (right column)**. The line colours below are: 'cycles' in blue, 'Instructions' in red, & 'branches' in yellow.

Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1: instructions & cycles count on WasmEdge

Mixtral-8x7b-instruct-v0.1: instructions & cycles count on Python/LLaMA.cpp

Llama-2-7B-Chat: instructions & cycles count on WasmEdge

Llama-2-7B-Chat: Instructions & cycles count on Python/LLaMA.cpp

Comparative performance profile patterns between WasmEdge and Python in 5 consecutive runs

Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1: instructions & cycles count on WasmEdge

Mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1: Instructions & cycles count on Python/LLaMA.cpp

Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha: instructions & cycles count on WasmEdge

No values produced for Huggingfaceh4_zephyr-7b-alpha in Python/LLaMA.cpp

Microsoft Phi-2: instructions & cycles count on WasmEdge

Microsoft Phi-2: Instructions & cycles count on Python/LLaMA.cpp

